

HAWASSA UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY
SCHOOL OF INFORMATICS
DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE

**REAL-TIME TOMATO LEAF DISEASE DETECTION AND
CLASSIFICATION USING PRE-TRAINED MODELS IN DEEP
LEARNING (RTTLDDC)**

MASTER'S THESIS
BY
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HAWASSA UNIVERSITY
HAWASSA, ETHIOPIA

May 10/2015

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**IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
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Declaration

I hereby declare that this MSc. Thesis is my original work and has not been presented in any other University and all sources of materials used for the thesis have been fully acknowledged.

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List of Abbreviation

<i>API</i>	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
<i>AWS</i>	<i>Amazon Web Service</i>
<i>BS</i>	<i>Bacterial Spot</i>
<i>CPUs</i>	<i>Central Processing Unit</i>
<i>CSS</i>	<i>Cascading Style Sheets</i>
<i>CNN</i>	<i>Convolutional Neural Network</i>
<i>CM</i>	<i>Confusion Matrix</i>
<i>DT</i>	<i>Decision Trees</i>
<i>DNN</i>	<i>Deep Neural Network</i>
<i>EB</i>	<i>Early Blight</i>
<i>GPU</i>	<i>Graphics Processing Unit</i>
<i>GB</i>	<i>Giga Byte</i>
<i>GUI</i>	<i>Graphical User Interface</i>
<i>HTML</i>	<i>Hypertext Markup Language</i>
<i>HIS</i>	<i>Hue, Saturation, and Intensity</i>
<i>IDE</i>	<i>Integrated Developer Environment</i>
<i>IP</i>	<i>Internet Protocol</i>
<i>IEEE</i>	<i>Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers.</i>
<i>ILSVRC</i>	<i>Image Net Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge</i>
<i>KNN</i>	<i>K-nearest Neighbors</i>
<i>LM</i>	<i>Leaf Mold</i>
<i>LB</i>	<i>Late Blight</i>
<i>LTSC</i>	<i>Long-Term Servicing Channel</i>
<i>MV</i>	<i>Mosaic Virus</i>
<i>MRC</i>	<i>Melkasa Research Center</i>
<i>NO</i>	<i>Neural Network</i>
<i>NNAPI</i>	<i>Neural Networks API</i>
<i>OS</i>	<i>Operating System</i>
<i>PDF</i>	<i>Portable Document Format.</i>

RNN	<i>Recurrent Neural Network</i>
RELU	<i>Rectified Linear Unit</i>
RGB	<i>Red, Green, and Blue</i>
RDC	<i>Remote Desktop Connection</i>
RTTLDDC	<i>Real-Time Tomato Leaf Disease Detection and Classification</i>
RTTLDDP	<i>Real-Time Tomato Leaf Disease Detection and Prediction</i>
SVM	<i>Support Vector Machines</i>
SSM	<i>Spotted-Spider-Mite</i>
SGS	<i>School of Graduate Study</i>
SLP	<i>Septorial Leaf Spot</i>
SoC	<i>System on Chip</i>
SVM	<i>Support Vector Machines</i>
TPUs	<i>Tensor Processing Units</i>
TFJS	<i>Tensor Flow Java Script</i>
TS	<i>Target Spot</i>
TPUs	<i>Tensor Processing Units</i>
UAAIE	<i>Upper Awash Agro Industry Enterprise</i>
UI	<i>User Interface</i>
URL	<i>Uniform Resource Locator</i>
VGG	<i>Visual Geometry Group, University of Oxford</i>
YLCV	<i>Yellow Leaf Curl Virus</i>

Abstract

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is one of the most grown vegetable plants in the world, second to potato and sweet potato. Detection of tomato leaf diseases through the naked eye is ineffective because there are numerous plant leaf diseases that are not visible early on plant leaf. There are a number of causes that limits tomato yield: - some of this is caused by bacteria, vires, and fungus. Deep learning become the most accurate and precise paradigms for the detection of plant diseases. Leaves of infected tomatoes are collected and labeled according to their disease categories. Datasets were collected from different farm fields in Ethiopia with the help of pathogens experts. 2000 tomato leaves image were collected for all 10 classes of tomato diseases and healthy. This collected dataset was augmented to increase our dataset from 2000 to 10,000. In the study nine type of tomato disease classes and one healthy class, totally 10 classes were considered. We had used pre-trained models that were based on deep learning paradigm and CNN architecture. Running time and highest accuracy were the criteria to select top five pre-trained models from Dictionary with models. InceptionV3, MobilenetV2, Resnet152V2, EfficientnetB3 and CNN models were selected and used in this study. Lightweight mode is derived by using quantization techniques from CNN model and used in developed prototype system (Web app). Real-Time Tomato Leaf Diseases Detection and Classification Prototype system is developed to detect and classify the tomato leaf disease at real time from the farm field. The preprocessed dataset is split in different splitting ratios (60:20:20 or 70:15:15 or 80:10:10), and 0.0001 or 0.0005 learning rate is used. We have read and analyze different literatures and the gap of that literature is they use machine learning models for classification purpose but machine learning models are old and need human intervention for feature extraction. And none of the models used for real time disease detection and classification. The selected pre-trained models and derived model have different accuracy value after trained with the same dataset. Maximum testing accuracy from all used selected pre- trained models and developed model is 99.99% (Efficientnetb3 model), while minimum test accuracy from all used models is 95.23% (TFLite model). Maximum loss from all selected and developed models was 0.5443, while minimum loss is 0.195. The TFLite model (derived from CNN model) is different from other models since it is integrated (embedded) on android application and works on smartphones. Because of it is deployed on smartphone, it is portable model and used for real-time disease detection and classification at farm fields (on-time prediction). It is also compatible with edge devices that used for real-time disease detection and classification.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks, Tomato Leaf Diseases Classification, TFLite model, Pre-Trained models, Dictionary with models, Real-Time

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Background to the Study

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) is one of the most widely consumed vegetable crops in the world[1]. It is a nutritionally well-balanced food that contains a substantial amount of vitamin A and vitamin C, thus it plays an important role in ensuring food security and nutrition. Globally, among horticultural products, tomato ranks third for volumes of production – after potato and sweet potato and first in terms of processing volumes. By its high yields per hectare and its processing potential, it is one of the strategic commodities prioritized by the farmer for their consumption and agro-industry. Tomato is a popular and widely grown vegetable crop in Ethiopia, ranking 8th in terms of annual national production. It is consumed in every household in different modes. In Ethiopia Tomato cultivated in certain areas, such as Walo, Hararge, Shawa, Jimma, Arsi, and Wallaga, it is also an important co-staple food [2].

Tomato grows on mostly any well-drained farm and Nine out of 10 farmers grow tomatoes in their field. Many gardeners also grow tomatoes in their gardens to use freshly grown tomatoes in their kitchens and get a good taste of food. The tomato plant is cultivated in all seasons but typically during winter and summer seasons. The plant cannot resist severe frost. It nurtures well under an average monthly temperature range of 21°C to 23°C but commercially it may be grown at temperatures ranging from 18°C to 27°C. Temperature and light intensity affect the pigmentation, fruit sets, and nutritive value of tomato fruits [3].

However, farmers and gardeners are sometimes unable to get proper progress in plant growth. The tomato's fruit may not sometimes appear on the plants or sometimes the tomatoes may get bad-looking and disease-full black spots at the bottom part. The identification of tomato plant disease may start by diagnosing the portion of the plant leaf having an infection and then to noting the differences such as brown or black patches and holes in the plant looking to look for insects also. The tomato problems may be divided into two sections: This is parasitic (bacterial, viral, fungi, pests, weeds, nematodes, etc.) and non-parasitic (irradiation, mineral miss-use, high or low temperature, toxicity in soil, air, and water, etc.) diseases. Bacteria or fungi or poor cultivation habits causing 16 diseases while insects causing 5 other types of diseases [4].

Plant disease recognition using images from digital cameras and mobile phones proves to be a significant challenge. The recent trend, the use of various machine learning algorithms for plant disease classification has shown promising results in a few selected diseases and crops[5]. The evolution of deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) based architectures has further enhanced the accuracy of classification significantly[6].

The diseases affect the crop at different growth stages in the farm field. Several factors limit tomato yield, these include pests, weeds, and diseases. Yield losses of 100% are common, particularly when tomatoes are infected early in development. The most common method used detection technique of the farmers were, using naked eyes, which required experience that depends on the farmer’s knowledge they get from their ancestors. Another method is advice from experts which is very rare at the gate in Ethiopia.

All diseases have common characteristics that change some morphological characteristics such as color or shape. These changes can be extracted through image segmentation and classification of different diseases through the Multiclass algorithm[3]. This is the Structure of the general category of plant diseases (taken from [7])

Figure 1: Structure of general category of plant diseases

1.1.1 Plant Leaf Diseases

A plant disease is any physiological or structural abnormality that is caused by a living organism[7]. The leaf of plant indicates the whether the plant is affected by diseases or is healthy. So, an impairment of the normal state of a plant that interrupts its vital functions or a malfunctioning process that is caused by continuous irritation and produces symptoms is called plant disease. Plant leaf diseases can be categorized based on the causal agents (i.e., infectious or noninfectious). Infectious plant leaf diseases are caused by a disease agent called a pathogen (pathogenic organism), which includes viruses, bacteria, nematodes, fungi, etc. This pathogenic organism is easily reproduced itself on the host (affected plant) and distributed from one host to another. But noninfectious plant leaf diseases can rise due to informal environmental

conditions such as high or low temperature, deficiency or excess of water, lack of oxygen and or mineral and, toxicity of the air or water, or soil.

1.2 Motivation for the Study

Plant disease detection is a critical topic that has been studied over the years and is motivated by the need to produce healthy food and keep food secure. After we observe Upper Awash Agro Industry Enterprise, which is large tomato farming and processing company in Ethiopia, the expert informs us about tomato plant diseases that repeatedly occur and destruct the tomato farm year to year. As the expert said, the way they diagnose the tomato plant disease and the treatment they gave was still traditional and affects the growing tomato and sometimes the treatment also do not cure plant. From our observation, we understand that even if the expert participates in the farm field they cannot recognize tomato plant diseases exactly with naked-eye approach. So, a new way is required to easily identify tomato plant diseases based on the features of the plant. To make this need to effect, image processing using deep learning is the best way to detect and classify plant leaf diseases. However, some desirable elements to consider should be cost-effectiveness, user-friendliness, sensitiveness, and accuracy. Plant diseases are caused by various factors such as viruses, bacteria, fungi, etc. But all diseases are detected or recognized by image processing techniques. In addition to image processing, a real time plant disease detector or web app (android application) helps the farmers to easily detect their tomato plant disease by using the smart phone they have on their hand.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

The plant in despairing for so many reasons, one of these reasons is disease. This causes change in Weather condition, lack of food for human and animal, loss in economy, loss in human power and time. Some tomato plant diseases are Known by the naked eye, but not possible to know which types of diseases and which chemical treatment is to be given. Sometime Tomato leaf disease affects the product without indicating any change on the outer part of the leaf. Which is difficult to identify the disease with traditional approaches? In other case Some Tomatoes don't produce fruit, while it normally grown-up (invisible destruction). Different Problems (Constraints) in Tomato Production in Ethiopia[2][8]. Even though some researchers develop the models that predict the disease using the image of the plant leaf, but researchers did not develop real time detection application that detect plant leaf disease directly from the farm fields by using their smart phone and internet.

In Ethiopia, farmers and investors detect the disease by naked eye observation which is a traditional approach. Some tomato diseases affect the whole farm within 24 hours, which destroys the whole tomato farm within a few days. The destruction of the tomato farms can cause a loss in the economy, time, manpower, and loss in food security. Plant disease recognition using the naked-eye is a major challenge

since many diseases are caused by Viruses, Bacteria, and Fungi. Different types of leaf disease affect tomatoes[3], [9]. Diagnosing and detecting of these plant leaf diseases are very important to cure and control the spreading of diseases. Image processing becomes the key technique for the diagnosis of various features of the plant in the areas of agriculture. Adding Real-Time detection (on time disease detection) to image processing techniques enhances the tomato leaf disease detection process to a portable and accessible service.

This study attempts to solve the problem by answering the following research questions.

- What are the most suitable image processing techniques for detecting tomato leaf diseases?
- How to select pre-trained models in deep learning for tomato leave diseases detection?
- How to develop (derive) **lightweight model** from selected pre-trained models that used for real time disease detection and classification on smartphones?
- What are the significant features that can be used to identify tomato disease?
- How to detect and classify the Tomato Leaf Disease using derived (developed) and selected Pre-trained model in deep learning?

1.4 Objective of the Study

1.4.1 General Objective:

The general objective of the study is to develop (derive) a Real-Time Tomato Leaf Disease detection, and classification model that can recommend prevention and a chemical treatment by integrating it to prototype system (web app).

1.4.2 Specific Objectives:

To achieve the above-mentioned general objective the following specific tasks should be performed.

- Gather data (image) of tomato leave from the farm field using camera and smart phone
- Apply image preprocessing to smooth the collected images for farther process.
- Selecting the best pre-trained deep learning classification models.
- Train the pre-trained algorithms with the preprocessed tomato leave dataset.
- Evaluate the models using different evaluation metrics.
- Developing a prototype system (Web app) for real-time tomato leave disease detection & classification.

1.5 Scope and Limitation of the Study

1.5.1 Scope of the Study

- This study focuses on designing and implementing a model that can automatically detect if a tomato plant leaf is infected by one of the nine types of disease or health.
- The study also focuses on the designing and implementing of a model that can automatically detect tomato leaf disease at in real-time on the farm field and recommend the prevention and important chemical treatment.
- In the study Web app (android Application) is developed for real time tomato leaf disease detection.

1.5.2 Limitations of the Study

- In this study, due to a lack of resources and time sample dataset do no collected from all parts of the country (Ethiopia) where tomato is harvested.
- The research focuses only on the image of tomato leaves, not including flowers, fruits, roots, and stems.
- Only a few numbers of tomato leave disease (bacteria or virus or fungus) that causes tangible effects should be included in the study.
- The study does not cover all the types of tomato species and all temperatures weather conditions where tomatoes are cultivated.
- The Prototype system (Web app) cannot support local language (Language limitation).
- The prototype system does not work offline.
- Because of a lack of time, resource, and pathogens expert the study does not cover all tomato leaf diseases (only 9 out of 26 is considered in the study).

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study has different benefits for different stakeholders and researchers. It will be used in different agricultural sectors:

- Government and private industries that are working in agricultural sectors benefit from this study.
- The farmers and investors are beneficiaries of this study since real time tomato leaf disease detection and classification is used in farm filed easily.
- The study can also apply to other plant leaf disease detection and classification using image processing.
- The study helps practitioners and students who have interest to work in image processing and leaf disease detection.

- The study put a milestone on the usage of smartphones for real-time disease detection and classification in the farm field, in addition to call, internet and other service that used by smart phone.

1.7 Structure of the Thesis

In the study the Thesis is structured as the following: The next chapter which is chapter Two discusses the Literature Reviews, related work, tomato disease symptom and Digital image processing were explained. Chapter three discusses the research methodologies. In this chapter data collection methods, material and tools used for conducting the study, architecture used selected model is discussed. Evaluation methods are also discussed. Subsequently chapter Four explains architecture design and implementation. Chapter Five explain the result of experimentation and discusses of the experimentation. Finally, Chapter Six discuss the research by using contribution, recommendation and conclusion.

Chapter Two: Literature Review and Related Works

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter literature review and related work is included. This helps to understand what scholars has done in the early research and identify the gap that the research has. The chapter is sub divided in to sections and finally the summary of the literature review is explained. In this chapter nine different tomato diseases were discussed. Pre-trained models in deep learning that were used in the study were explained. Computer vision, deep learning and digital image processing is also discussed.

2.2 Tomato Plant over View

Agricultural productivity is something on which economy highly depends[10]. This is the one of the reasons that disease detection in plants plays an important role in agriculture field, as having disease in plants are quite natural. Ethiopian economy is highly dependent on agriculture, since most of the population is farmer. This implies farming have high impact on country's GDP (Gross Domestic Product). Plant disease cause high destruction, if it is not protected at early stages. Plant disease reduces both quality and quantity of the agricultural products. Here are two different types of plant diseases. This is parasitic cause disease and nonparasitic cause diseases. Pathologist classifies the plant disease based on parts of plant, like root, stem, leaf, and flower and fruit disease. Parasitic Couse plant disease is pathogen disease, pests and weeds. While non-parasitic Couse disease includes water borne diseases, temperature and light intensity Couse disease and lack or excess of minerals.

Figure 2: Tomato Disease Sample Images

2.3 Tomato Leaf Diseases

Tomatoes are usually vigorous growers that will reward you with a bumper crop when grown in full sun with plenty of water and nutrients (these plants tend to be heavy feeders, so they do best in rich soil with supplemental fertilizer). But it's almost inevitable that these plants will end up with a foliar disease or blemished fruit.

2.3.1 Tomato-Early-Blight

Early Blight of tomato plant is caused by the fungus known as *Alternaria Solana*. This disease causes direct losses by the infection of fruits and indirect losses by reducing plant vigor[11]. The main symptom of early blight is round leaf spots with a characteristic target appearance due to the dark concentric rings that develop in most spots. They are about .5 inch in diameter. Spots first appear on older leaves near the base of the plant. The causal fungal pathogen also produces symptoms on stems and fruit. Young seedlings can be killed by stem lesions developing at their base. Sources of the pathogen are infested seed, debris from infected plants left in or on the soil (where it can survive at least 1 year), and spores from other affected plants dispersed typically short distances by wind, water, insects, or animals.

2.3.2 Tomato-Late-Blight

Late blight caused by *Phytophthora infestans*, a waits the tomato where it is cultivated in moist, cool, rainy, and humid environments[12]. Leaf symptoms of late blight first appear as small, water-soaked areas that rapidly enlarge to form purple-brown, oily-appearing blotches. On the lower side of leaves, rings of grayish-white mycelium and spore-forming structures may appear around the blotches. Entire leaves die and infections quickly spread to petioles and young stems. Infected fruit turn brown but remain firm unless infected by secondary decay organisms; symptoms usually begin on the shoulders of the fruit because spores land on fruit from above. Late blight, caused by *Phytophthora infestans*, is an important and destructive disease on tomato[13].

2.3.3 Tomato-Leaf-Mold

Tomato leaf mold is caused by a fungal pathogen called *Passalora fulva* (syn. *Cladosporium fulvum*)[14]. It is an ascomycete fungus that lives on living tomato leaves. The fungus produces conidia that infect the lower surfaces of leaves. Upon landing on leaves, the fungus lands and enters plant stomata used in gas exchange. The stomata become clogged and tomato plants cannot respire well, resulting in wilting, defoliation, and infection. Disease symptoms first appear after seven days as light green spots on leaves[15]. Soon after, olive-green asexual conidia emerge, and eventually the spots become necrotic. Disease symptoms appear first on the lower leaves of tomato plants. Fruit production may not be severely hampered during the earlier stages of disease, but over time, disease severity increases and defoliation

occurs. Proper identification of disease is important. Abiotic conditions such as magnesium deficiency and the beginning stages of other diseases can produce similar symptoms to tomato leaf mold.

2.3.4 Tomato-Septorial-Leaf-Spot

Septorial leaf spot is caused by a fungus, *Septorial lycopersici*[16]. It is one of the most destructive diseases of tomato foliage and is particularly severe in areas where wet, humid weather persists for extended periods. Septorial leaf spot usually appears on the lower leaves after the first fruit sets[16]. Spots are circular, about 1/16 to 1/4 inch in diameter with dark brown margins and tan to gray centers with small black fruiting structures. Characteristically, there are many spots per leaf. This disease spreads upwards from oldest to youngest growth. If leaf lesions are numerous, the leaves turn slightly yellow, then brown, and then wither. Fruit infection is rare. The fungus overwinters on infected tomato debris or on weeds in the nightshade family, the same family to which tomatoes belong. The fungus can also survive on equipment such as plant stakes and cages. Long periods of high relative humidity, temperatures of 60–80 degrees F, and leaf wetness are ideal conditions for development and spread of the pathogen.

2.3.5 Tomato-Spider-Mites (Two –Spotted-Spider-Mite)

Two-spotted spider mites are occasional pests that can cause serious damage to some vegetable crops during hot dry weather.[17] Mites can injure tomatoes, beans, muskmelons, watermelons, and sweet corn. Extended periods of hot, dry weather favors mite buildups[18]. Infestations usually first occur at the edge of a field, typically near rank weed growth or dirt roads.

Generally, mites feed on the undersides of leaves. They use their sucking mouth parts to remove sap from plants, giving the upper leaf surface a speckled or mottled appearance. Leaves of mite-infested plants may turn yellow and dry up, and plants may lose vigor and die when infestations are severe. The undersides of affected leaves appear tan or yellow and have a crusty texture. Heavy infestations of the two-spotted spider mite produce fine webbing that may cover the entire plant. Mites are identified by shaking symptomatic leaves onto a sheet of white paper or by observing infected leaf areas with a hand lens. In hot dry weather, mites can cause plants to drop leaves in a few weeks. Fruit from severely infested plants are often unmarketable because defoliated plants tend to yield small, poor quality fruit.

2.3.6 Tomato-Target-Spot

Target spot of tomato is caused by the fungal pathogen *Corynespora cassiicola*[19][20]. The disease occurs on field-grown tomatoes in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. Target spot infections reduce yield indirectly by reducing the photosynthetic area and directly by reducing the fruit's marketability through fruit spots. Tomato plants have been infected with strains of the pathogen isolated

from other hosts in greenhouse tests. However, some isolates of the pathogen have shown some host specificity while others have a wider host range. The fungus function as a necrotroph (killing tissue as it infects), a saprophyte (surviving on plant debris), and as an epiphyte (growing on but not infecting plant tissues). Epiphytic colonization of weeds can provide inoculum for tomatoes.

The target spot fungus can infect all above-ground parts of the tomato plant.[21] Plants are most susceptible as seedlings and just before and during fruiting. The initial foliar symptoms are pinpoint-sized, water-soaked spots on the upper leaf surface. The spots develop into small, necrotic lesions that have light brown centers and dark margins. These symptoms may be confused with symptoms of bacterial spot. The lesions increase in size, become circular with gray to pale brown centers. As the lesions enlarge, they can develop darker concentric circles, hence, the name target spot. The concentric circles are similar to those seen on early blight lesions. Yellow halos can form around the lesions on some varieties. Lesions can coalesce, forming large blighted areas on the leaflets, and infected leaves may drop prematurely. Target spot infections typically start on the older, lower leaves in the inner canopy. Thus, the initial symptoms may not be noticed by the grower, making early detection difficult. The disease progresses upward, causing defoliation of the inner canopy, a condition known as “melting-out”.

2.3.7 Tomato-Mosaic-Virus

Tomato mosaic virus member of genus Potexvirus which infects mainly solanaceous plants, including tomato, potato and tobacco[22].Tomato mosaic virus is one of the oldest described plant viruses. It is extremely easily spread and can be devastating to crops. Tomato mosaic virus is a serious and extremely contagious disease. It is also hard to identify, with symptoms varying wildly depending upon the variety and age of the infected plant, the strain of the virus, and environmental conditions. Tomato mosaic virus symptoms can be found at any stage of growth and all parts of the plant may be infected. They are often seen as a general mottling or mosaic appearance on foliage. When the plant is severely affected, leaves may look akin to ferns with raised dark green regions. Leaves may also become stunted[23]. Infected plants may have a severe reduction in fruit set and those that do set may be dotted with yellow blotches and necrotic spots while the interior of the fruit is brown. Stems, petioles, leaves, and fruit may all show signs of infection.

2.3.8 Tomato-Yellow-Leaf-Curl-Virus

TYLCV is an Old World geminivirus, first described in the Middle East in the 1960s [24]. Tomato yellow leaf curl virus (TYLCV) can infect over 30 different kinds of plants, but it is mainly known to cause devastating losses of up to 100 per cent in the yield of tomatoes[25]. Both field and glasshouse grown tomatoes are susceptible. TYLCV is vectored by silverleaf whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*). TYLCV is a begomovirus, implying it has a wide host range on dicotyledons. There are two strains of TYLCV, a mild

strain and a severe strain. The mild strain was considered responsible for the recent detection of TYLCV in tomato and weed plants in northern Victoria (David Lovelace pers. comm). The severe strain infects bean and tomato. The most obvious symptoms in tomato plants are small leaves that become yellow between the veins. The leaves also curl upwards and towards the middle of the leaf. In seedlings, the shoots become shortened and give the young plants a bushy appearance. In mature plants only, new growths produced after infection is reduced in size. Although tomato production is reduced by the infection, the fruit appears unaffected. TYLCV is transmitted from diseased to healthy plants by silverleaf whitefly, which feeds on a wide range of hosts. Levels of TYLCV can be correlated to the population size of its vector silverleaf whitefly. It is not known if native whiteflies can spread the virus.

2.3.9 Tomato-Bacterial-Spot

Tomato fruit in home gardens and commercial fields in Denver and the northern Front Range may sometimes develop a black spot disease unusual for our area. The disease symptoms are dark specks that become raised and scab-like as they enlarge. Sunken centers on older spots are common. Lesions are brown turning black and can appear blistered. The round spots can merge causing irregular-shaped patterns.

Bacterial spot is caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* sp. *vesicatoria* (X.c.v.) Bacteria[26]. It is something seldom seen in Colorado due to the dry climate suppressing most bacterial diseases. Some years, a wet early summer and higher humidity favor it. If people overhead water instead of ground irrigating they tend to help the disease. Hail and heavy wind-driven rains may inflict injuries on plants and help disease spread via wound entry. Bacterial spot develops on seedlings and mature plants. On seedlings, infections may cause severe defoliation[27]. On older plants, infections occur primarily on older leaves and appear as water-soaked areas. Leaf spots turn from yellow or light green to black or dark brown. Older spots are black, slightly raised, superficial and measure up to 0.3 inch (7.5 mm) in diameter. Larger leaf blotches may also occur, especially on the margins of leaves. Symptoms on immature fruit are at first slightly sunken and surrounded by a water-soaked halo, which soon disappears. Fruit spots enlarge, turn brown, and become scabby.

Table 1: Sample of Tomato Plant Diseases and Symptoms

<i>Name of the disease</i>	<i>Symptoms of the disease</i>	<i>Part of plant mainly disease affected</i>
Early Blight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early blight infection starts at the bottom of the plant with leaf spotting and yellowing. • Initially, small dark spots form on older foliage near the ground. • Larger spots have target-like concentric rings. • Severely infected leaves turn brown and fall off, or dead, dried leaves may cling to the stem. 	Foliage, leaves, fruit, and stem at any stage of development.
Late Blight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infected leaves typically have green to brown patches of dead tissue surrounded by a pale green or gray border. • When the weather is very humid and wet, late blight infections can appear water-soaked or dark brown in color, and are often described as appearing greasy. • White, fuzzy growth may be found on the undersides of leaves or on lower stems. • Stem and petiole lesions are brown and are typically not well defined in shape. • Discoloration may also occur on the flowers, causing them to drop. • Symptomatic tomato fruits appear mottled, often with golden to dark brown, firm, sunken surfaces. • White, fuzzy pathogen growth can also be found in association with the fruit lesions. 	Leave, fruit, stem, flower
Leaf Mold	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When the disease does manifest on the fruit, tomatoes with leaf mold become dark in color, leathery, and rot at the stem end. • The oldest leaves are infected first. Pale greenish-yellow spots, usually less than 1/4 inch, with no definite margins, form on the upper sides of leaves. • Olive-green to brown velvety mold forms on the lower leaf surface below leaf spots. • Leaf spots grow together and turn brown. Leaves wither and die but often remain attached to the plant. • Infected blossoms turn black and fall off. • Fruit infections start as a smooth black irregular area on the stem end of the fruit. As the disease progresses, the infected area becomes sunken, dry and leathery. 	Flowers, stems, fruit and leaf
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The first symptoms appear as small, water-soaked, circular spots 1/16 to 1/8" 	leaves, petioles,

Septoria-Leaf-Spot	<p>in diameter on the undersides of older leaves.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The centers of these spots then turn gray to tan and have a dark-brown margin. • The spots are distinctively circular and are often quite numerous. 	stems, and the calyx
Spider-Mites (Two-spotted-Spider-Mite)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leaves of mite-infested plants may turn yellow and dry up, and plants may lose vigor and die when infestations are severe • The undersides of affected leaf appear tan or yellow and have a crusty texture. Heavy infestations of the two-spotted spider mite produce fine webbing that may cover the entire plant. • Mites are identified by shaking symptomatic leaves onto a sheet of white paper or by observing infected leaf areas with a hand lens. 	Leave, fruit
Target Spot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The disease starts on the older leaves and spreads upwards. • The first signs are irregular-shaped spots (less than 1 mm) with a yellow margin. • Some of the spots enlarge up to 10 mm and show characteristics rings, hence the name of 'target spot'. • Spread to all leaflets and to other leaves is rapid, causing the leaves to turn yellow, collapse and die. • Spots also occur on the stems. They are long and thin. • Small light brown spots with dark margins may also occur on the fruit. • The spores are spread by wind-blown rain, and if windy wet weather continues for a few days, spread is fast and plants lose their leaves quickly. 	Leave, stem
Mosaic Virus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tomato mosaic virus symptoms can be found at any stage of growth and all parts of the plant may be infected. • To MV causes yellow mosaic symptoms on the leaves and tomato fruits. • Tomato mosaic virus symptoms are seen as a general mottling or mosaic appearance on foliage. • Light and darker green mosaic leaf mottle, sometimes with distortion of younger leaves; this is the most common reaction in summer in glasshouses. 	Leaves, fruits, foliage
Yellow-Leaf-Curl-Virus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most obvious symptoms in tomato plants are small leaves that become yellow between the veins. • The leaves also curl upwards and towards the middle of the leaf. • In seedlings, the shoots become shortened and give the young plants a bushy appearance. • In mature plants, only new growths produced after infection is reduced in size. Although tomato production is reduced by the infection, the fruit appears 	Leaves, fruits

	unaffected.	
Bacterial Spot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bacterial spot can affect all above ground parts of a tomato plant, including the leaves, stems, and fruit. • Bacterial spot appears on leaves as small (less than 1/8 inch), sometimes water-soaked (i.e., wet-looking) circular areas. • Spots may initially be yellow-green, but darken to brownish-red as they age. • When the disease is severe, extensive leaf yellowing and leaf loss can also occur. • On green fruit, spots are typically small, raised and blister-like, and may have a yellowish halo. • As fruit mature, the spots enlarge (reaching a maximum size of 1/4 inch) and turn brown, scabby and rough. • Mature spots may be raised, or sunken with raised edges. 	leaves, stems, and fruit

2.4 Computer Vision

Computer vision is a field of artificial intelligence (AI) that enables computers and systems to derive meaningful information from digital images, videos and other visual inputs and take actions or make recommendations based on that information. If AI (Artificial Intelligence) enables computers to think, computer vision enables them to see, observe and understand. Computer vision trains machines to perform these functions, but it has to do it in much less time with cameras, data and algorithms rather than retinas, optic nerves and a visual cortex. Because a system trained to inspect products or watch a production asset can analyze thousands of products or processes a minute, noticing imperceptible defects or issues, it can quickly surpass human capabilities.

Computer vision needs lots of data. It runs analyses of data over and over until it discerns distinctions and ultimately recognizes images. For example, to train a computer to recognize automobile tires, it needs to be fed vast quantities of tire images and tire-related items to learn the differences and recognize a tire, especially one with no defects.

Two essential technologies are used to accomplish this: a type of machine learning called deep learning and a convolutional neural network (CNN). Machine learning uses algorithmic models that enable a computer to teach itself about the context of visual data. If enough data is fed through the model, the computer will “look” at the data and teach itself to tell one image from another. Algorithms enable the machine to learn by it, rather than someone programming it to recognize an image. A CNN helps a machine learning or deep learning model “look” by breaking images down into pixels that are given tags or labels. It uses the labels to perform convolutions (a mathematical operation on two functions to

produce a third function) and makes predictions about what it is “seeing.” The neural network runs convolutions and checks the accuracy of its predictions in a series of iterations until the predictions start to come true. It is then recognizing or seeing images in a way similar to humans. Much like a human making out an image at a distance, a CNN first discerns hard edges and simple shapes, and then fills in information as it runs iterations of its predictions. A CNN is used to understand single images.

2.5 Deep Learning

Deep learning uses artificial neural networks to perform sophisticated computations on large amounts of data. It is a type of machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI) that imitates the way humans gain certain types of knowledge. Deep learning algorithms train machines by learning from examples. Deep learning is an important element of data science, which includes statistics and predictive modeling.

2.6 Deep Learning Pre-Trained Models

Pre-trained models are models that already trained with thousands class of plant diseases. This trained model can be used for prediction purpose by using transfer learning techniques (i.e. training once again the trained models). From the deep learning pre-trained models, we have used 27 pre-trained models to select top five best models that had highest accuracy output. Finally, the models that have the highest accuracy (top 5) were selected for this study. The selected top five models are explained in the following section:

2.6.1 ResNet152V2

According to literature [28] ResNet152V2 is a ResNet model with more layers than the commonly used ResNet50. Because tensor created additional layers take up more memory than ResNet50. CNN architecture with hundreds or thousands of convolutional layers is known as a Residual Network (ResNet)[29]. ResNet has a large number of layers and is extremely fast. The main difference between ResNetV2 and the original (V1) is that V2 applies batch normalization to each weight layer before applying it. ResNet has great performance in image recognition and localization tasks, demonstrating the importance of numerous visual recognition tasks.

2.6.2 MobileNetV2

Mobile Net[30] is a deep learning architecture that focuses on the mobile platform where the computational resource is limited. An improved version, which is called MobileNetV2, is then introduced by Google with slight modifications to the original version. The basis of the network still remains the same, which is separable convolution. According literature[31] Mobile Net architecture is developed to run vision applications on embedded and mobile platforms. Mobile models have been built on increasingly more efficient building blocks. MobileNetV2 introduced depth wise separable convolutions

as an efficient replacement for traditional convolution layers [32]. It also introduced the linear bottleneck and inverted residual structure in order to make even more efficient layer structures by leveraging the low rank nature of the problem[33]. MobileNetV2 architecture used inverted bottleneck blocks and residual connections to replace expensive convolutions which decrease the number of operations and memory needed while retaining the same accuracy[34].

2.6.3 CNN

CNN is a special neural network model proposed by LeCun,[35] which is used for document image recognition, and has made a great breakthrough in image classification and retrieval, target detection and so on. Deep CNN reduces the dimensions of image by increasing the number of hidden layer (convolutional layer and sampling layer), and extracts the sparse image features in low-dimensional space. Because of their weights sharing, CNN has much fewer neurons and parameters and so it is easier to train[36]. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are the type of deep learning models that are particularly well-suited for image classification tasks. They are able to learn features directly from the input data and have been successful in a wide range of applications, including object recognition, face detection, and image generation[31].

2.6.4 EfficientNetb3

Efficient Nets is a network series published by Google in May 2019[37]. They designed a baseline network using neural architecture search, and scaled the model to obtain a series of models. Its accuracy and efficiency are better than all previous convolutional networks. In particular, Efficient Net-B7 achieved a state-of-the-art top-1 accuracy of 84.4% on ImageNet, while being 8.4 times smaller and 6.1 times faster than the previous best convolutional network.

Efficient Net is a convolutional neural network design and scaling method that uniformly scales all dimensions of depth, width, and resolution using a compound coefficient[38]. With a set of predefined scaling coefficients, this model scales network width, depth, and resolution equally. Efficient Net is used because it is higher accuracy and better efficiency over existing CNNs[39]. And this model uniformly scales network width, depth, and resolution with a set of fixed scaling coefficients.

2.6.5 Inception V3

According to literature[40] six state-of-the-art architectures (Alex Net, Dense Net, Inception V3, ResNet-50, SqueezeNet-1.1 and VGG13) were trained on the Plant Village dataset. Inception_v3 gave the best accuracy for the deep training strategy. The inception in Inception_v3 is the most prominent characteristic. Its core idea is factorization, replacing the big convolutional kernel with multiple smaller

kernels. The inception mechanism not only reduces calculations but also improves feature extraction capabilities[41].

Furthermore, these models allow us to fine-tune and transfer learning from a task where we have a large labeled dataset to a particular task as disease classification. In the case of small training datasets, the pre-trained model achieved faster convergence and higher accuracy[42].

2.7 Related Works

Using deep learning in image processing is very promising and profitable proposition at this time. There are a lot of researches in this area using various methodology and different algorithms that was done by different researchers in the world. Considering different types of plant diseases that Cause a huge destruction in few days, developing the system that easily detect and classify the disease and suggest the solution is crucial and very important thing. Since manually identifying and preventing plant diseases is very difficult, using technology that support to identify the problem and helps to acquire the solution is very important.

The ultimate goal of plant disease detection and classification using deep CNN architecture was to enhance agriculture by providing current state-of-art solutions. As a result, the quality and quantity of agricultural products increase, and the resource and money required for plant disease detection and classification will be minimized. This section summarizes all the related work done by other researchers on tomato plant disease detection and classification

Simonyan, et al [43] used VGG 16 model which is the CNN architecture created by VGG (Visual Geometry Group, University of Oxford) for the ILSVRC-2014 (ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge). In this study authors try to evaluate deep convolutional networks (up to 19 weight layers) for large scale image classification. The Authors investigate the effect of convolutional network depth on its accuracy in the large-scale image recognition setting. They obtained final accuracy of 77.2% when they trained the code for 1000 epochs on NVIDIA super computer. In the study, disease detection is based on the image of leaf of tomato plant. This model does not work for real time disease detection and classification and had poor testing accuracy.

Szegedy et al [44] proposed, Inception V3 model which has a 42-layer deep learning network with fewer parameters. The authors provide several design principles to scale up convolutional networks and studied in the context of inception architecture. To detect and classify the disease of tomato plant, they used the image of leaf of tomato. They found the accuracy is 63.4 when they trained for 1000 epochs on NVIDIA.

As the testing accuracy indicates their model had poor testing accuracy which may have effect on disease detection and classification.

Howard et al, [45] Mobile Net, was proposed in 2017 and comes with keras package of python. In this model the authors used python library to process the training, validating and testing datasets. With title of efficient convolutional neural networks for mobile vision applications, the authors found 63.7% accuracy with 1000 epochs it gave on our 10-class **tomato** disease problem. From these 10 classes one is the healthy class. The authors used the image of leaf of tomato plant for disease detection. Even though the author tries to use model for mobile device and use python libraries to process training and testing, the model testing accuracy were poor and cannot work for on time prediction.

Mohit Agarwal et al [46] proposed CNN (Model), where the model contain 3 convolution and 3 max pooling layers followed by 2 fully connected layer. For experimentation purpose they take the images of leaf of **tomato** plant from plant village dataset. The authors get accuracy of 91.5% for 9 diseases and 1 healthy class, when they trained the code for 1000 epochs on NVIDIA super computer. This model testing accuracy was good, but do not work for real time disease detection and classification and also the model does not work on edge device like smartphones.

Zewdu Tiunay [47]used CNN model to detect and classify tomato leaf disease. The author used some data from farm field and some data from plant village dataset. He organizes six diseases and one healthy category of **tomato** plant. The author uses the image of leaf of tomato for disease detection. After experimentation the final accuracy of the model was 95.62%, which is good. But, the author does not use the same number of images for all classes (e.g. yellow leaf curly = 3209 images and leaf mold = 952 images) in the study. This is a problem and if the author failed to handle this problem then the model will become a disaster because modeling using class-imbalanced data is biased in favor of the majority class. It also may have effect on model average accuracy and the whole model performance. This model does not use for real time disease detection and classification.

Sagar Vetal et al. proposed image processing techniques to detect tomato plant disease. The Authors use image segmentation for parting affected part of the image and Multicast SVM algorithm to identify the disease. Initial stage raw image is taken as input and smoothen through various techniques like thresholding, greyscale conversion, RGB to HIS various filters like median filter, CIBAL color model to remove noise and many more image smoothing techniques are used. But since the SVM deal with binary system only, it can classify only two inputs. The histogram matching method of SVM also gives poor accuracy results. Even though the accuracy result shows high value the number of data sets used for the study is very small which 80 tomato images for each disease.

Sumita Mishra, et al. Proposed Real-time Corn Plant Disease Recognition system by using deep neural network model. The author uses different devices for image processing which help them to detect the plant disease live from the farm field. After they train the DNN on the computer which has GPU using Keras API they migrate from high performance GPU to mobile device with limited computational capability. Authors use mobile device for image processing when new plant leaf images are captured. The trained DNN model is deployed on to the Intel Movidius NCS, a system on chip (SoC) using NSDSK toolkit. Finally, the author found 98.40 % accuracy result on high-processing device and 88.4% on mobile devices which is with low computational performance. The number of images the authors use is very small. The device used for real-time disease detection is not cheap for users to use only for a time.

Aravind Krishnaswamy Rangarajan, et al. proposed Tomato crop disease classification using a pre-trained deep learning algorithm. The Authors performed classification with the images from the Plant Village dataset using pre-trained deep learning architecture namely AlexNet and VGG16 net. The classification accuracy using 13,262 images was 97.29% for VGG16 net and 97.49% for AlexNet. Both the training dataset and test dataset collected from the plant village dataset for pre-trained deep learning algorithms which may make the model memorizing rather than predicting, while testing the accuracy.

Table 2: Related Work and Gaps

<i>Authors</i>	<i>Research title</i>	<i>Model used And Test Accuracy</i>	<i>Research gap</i>
Simonyan, et al	Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition	VGG 16 77.2%	- high network usage - high storage usage - No real-time disease detection
Szegedy et al	Rethinking the inception architecture for computer vision	Inception V3 63.4 %	- No real-time disease detection - the quality of camera (images) not known
Howard et al	Efficient convolutional neural networks for mobile vision applications	Mobile Net 63.7%	- No real-time disease detection - the quality of the camera (images) not known
Mohit Agarwal et al	Tomato leaf disease detection using convolution neural network (CNN)	CNN 91.5%	- No real-time disease detection - the quality of the camera (images) is not known
Zewdu Tiumay	Tomato Leaf Diseases Detection and Classification using Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)	CNN 95.62%	- The number of images in each category is not equal (e.g. 3209 and 1000) which may have an effect on average accuracy and make the model biased. - used imbalanced classes, which cause model disaster because of modeling using class-imbalanced data is biased in favor of the majority

			<p>class</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collected dataset source (farm field) is not known - The participation of pathogen expert is not specified for the collected dataset, which may indicate there is no collected dataset the from farm field. - Datasets size is small since author have used plant village site, so can use large dataset. - Only 5 disease type is detected which is not enough compared to real problem. - Not work for real time disease detection - Quality of camera (images) not known - The model does not work on smartphone, hence difficult to solve the real problem on the ground
Sagar Vetal et al.	Tomato Plant Disease Detection using Image Processing	Multi-class SVM model 93.5%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Small number of data set is used which may have effect on accuracy when large number of datasets is used. - not work for real time disease detection
Sumita Mishra, et al	Deep Convolutional Neural Network based Detection System for Real-time Corn Plant Disease Recognition	CNN 98.40%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The number of diseases the researcher tries to classify is very few when compared to real word disease. - The number of the data set used from the farm filed is very small. - Hardware the authors used can work locally without internet access, but the cost of the device is not cheap for farmer.
Aravind Krishnaswamy Rangarajan, et al.	Tomato crop disease classification using pre-trained deep learning algorithm	AlexNet = 97.49% VGG16net = 97.29%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All the dataset is collected from plant village and the author's uses the pre-trained model, so model memorizes may happen. - The number of the dataset is small since the author has a chance to large number of datasets from the plant village.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

3.1 General Structure of this Chapter

In this chapter different section of the study is discussed. This are research flow, problem definition, Literature Review, data collection methods, material used for conducting the research, design and development of web app, implementation and evaluation of selected models is discussed.

3.2 Research Flow

The entire process of research is broken down into three phases. In Phase I, the problem is defined by reviewing literature and observation which leads to an objective formulation that is divided into general and specific. In the second phase, the data were prepared and partitioned into three sets that are training, validation, and testing set. After the data partition, different deep learning pre-trained models were selected. In the third phase, different pre-trained models have experimented with different hyper parameters. Then, the models are evaluated by the evaluation metrics and research report is generated.

Figure 3: Research Flow diagram

3.3 Problem Definition

In the problem formulation stage, we had tried to identify the main limitation in the current Research that is related to tomato plant leaf detection and classification and find out the possible solution for the identified problem. In most literatures, researchers develop the model that can detect and classify the disease but they cannot include real time plant disease detection. This study is focused on real time tomato leaf disease detection and classification. We had retrain the

selected pre-trained models once again because of the model that are pre-trained are not trained with dataset that were collected from Ethiopia, since symptom of the disease may vary from country to country due to differences in weather conditions, soil, mineral, temperature, and water in the farm field. So, collecting datasets from Ethiopian farm fields and retraining the pre-trained models help to increase the model performance to detect and classify tomato leaf disease in Ethiopia. And also datasets that were hosted on the cloud is not ours and do not collect from Ethiopia.

3.4 Literature Review

For conducting the research, different literature is reviewed (Internet, journals and etc.) to understand the concept of image processing and pre-trained deep learning models, how they applied to solve the related problem in the prior research. During the revision of this literature, the gap of the previous solution will be identified to use as input for this proposed solution. This is the important and necessary content where all possible reference and journal related to research is investigated and analyzed. Some of the literature that has been reviewed is shows in the following diagram:

Figure 4: Literature Source (Library) of the Research

3.5 Data Collection Methods

We had collected tomato leaves using camera and smart phone. In addition to collected dataset from farm field, we had used the collected dataset from the expert (farm site expert). Our Dataset was collected from Arsi zone, in different location like mert (Awash River), golja (Ketar River), Melkasa Research Center and Upper awash agro industry enterprise. This dataset is collected at different time and the number of collected dataset is different from location to location. The study includes nine (9) disease classes of tomato plant and one healthy class. Where each classis has totally 1000 sample tomato leave images. Total sample images were ten thousand ($10 \times 1000 = 10000$).

Tomato Leaf images are used in identifying the affected area of leaf by using image processing techniques. Various image-processing techniques are applied on them, to process raw images, to get useful image for further processing and analysis. We should use augmentation techniques to balance the images inside the class (if any loss of images is occurred during experimentation) and to increase the number tomato leaves image in the dataset. We have used the following data collection (gathering) methods: -

3.5.1 Observation: -

We had observed physically the Upper Awash Agro industry enterprise (UAAIE) and Melkasa Research Center (MRC) farm fields and gather data with help of farm experts in farm sites. Pathogens-expert tell us how the diseases affect the plant in farm field and which diseases affect the tomato plant in farm filed repeatedly year to year.

3.5.2 Document Analysis: -

For more information about the tomato plant leaf disease, we had reviewed and analysis different research articles, panel papers, research repository, websites and different research library.

3.5.3 Interview: -

To get the basic information about the plant disease we had interviewed different farmers and farm experts. During data collection, some experts in Upper Awash Agro industry enterprise (UAAIE)) told as there are deferent tomato plant leaf diseases that occur in farm filed but 5 of them are repeatedly occur in the farm field year to year. These are: Powdery mildew, blight, septorial leaf spot, rust, wilt, etc. At different farm field different tomato diseases occur season to season the dataset contains images with nine tomato diseases and healthy leaf.

3.6 Data-Processing

Data processing is a method to perform some operations on an image, in order to get an enhanced image and or to extract some useful information from it. It also analysis and manipulate the digitized image, especially in order to improve its quality. It is basically signal processing in which input is an image and output is image or characteristics according to requirement associated with that image.

Digital-Image: An image may be defined as a two-dimensional function $f(x, y)$, where x and y are spatial (plane) coordinates, and the amplitude of fat any pair of coordinates (x, y) is called the intensity or grey level of the image at that point. In another word an image is nothing more than a two-dimensional matrix (3-D in case of colored images) which is defined by the mathematical function $f(x, y)$ at any point is giving the pixel value at that point of an image, the pixel value describes how bright that pixel is, and what color it should be. To make the data ready for further process we use the following steps: -

- Step 1: Image Acquisition is the very first step that requires capturing an image with the help of a digital camera or smart phone. Additional images will be regenerated by using the augmentation techniques to increase the number of images in datasets.
- Step2: Preprocessing of the input image to improve the quality of the image and to remove the undesired distortion from the image. Clipping of the leaf image is performed to get the interested image region.
- Step3: Image Augmentation: Image data augmentation is the process of generating new transformed versions of images from the given image dataset to increase its diversity. To a computer, images are just a 2-dimensional array of numbers. These numbers represent pixel values, which you can tweak in many ways to generate new, augmented images.
- Step4: Image Labeling: Image labeling is a type of data labeling where the goal is to add meaningful information to images. The task in general is to identify certain features or objects in an image, and then to use this information to select said objects in an image, to classify the image according to the presence of these features.
- Step5: Image segmentation is applied to simplify the illustration of the image with segments so that it can be easily analyzed. Image segmentation is performed to segment the disease affected and unaffected portions of the leaf.

Figure 5: Data Processing Sequence (steps)

3.6.1 Data Partitioning

The dataset is partitioned as Training, Validation and Test datasets. Training dataset is used to train the models to learn image features like curve, line, texture, region of interest (affected region) and so on. The Validation Datasets is used for model and hyper parameter selection and evaluation of the models. Finally Test datasets is used to measure the performance of selected models with unseen data. Depending on experimentation the collected data sets are split into three different train, valid, test ratios. These are:

- Training = 80%, Validation= 10%, Test =10%
- Training =70%, Validation = 15%, Test = 15%
- Training = 60%, Validation = 20%, Test = 20%

Table 3 : Dataset of Tomato Plant Disease Detection and classification (80%, 10%, 10%)

<i>Class or Category</i>	<i>No. of Training Images</i>	<i>No. of Validation Images</i>	<i>No. of Test Images</i>	<i>Total Images</i>
Early Blight	800	100	100	1000
Late Blight	800	100	100	1000
Leaf Mold	800	100	100	1000
Septorial-Leaf-Spot	800	100	100	1000
Spider-Mites (Two-spotted-Spider-Mite)	800	100	100	1000
Target Spot	800	100	100	1000
Mosaic Virus	800	100	100	1000
Yellow-Leaf-Curl-Virus	800	100	100	1000
Bacterial Spot	800	100	100	1000
Healthy	800	100	100	1000
Total Datasets				= 10,000

Table 4: Dataset of Tomato Plant Disease Detection and classification (70%, 15%, and 15%)

<i>Class or Category</i>	<i>No. of Training Images</i>	<i>No. of Validation Images</i>	<i>No. of Test Images</i>	<i>Total Images</i>
Early Blight	700	150	150	1000
Late Blight	700	150	150	1000
Leaf Mold	700	150	150	1000
Septorial-Leaf-Spot	700	150	150	1000
Spider-Mites (Two-spotted-Spider-Mite)	700	150	150	1000
Target Spot	700	150	150	1000
Mosaic Virus	700	150	150	1000
Yellow-Leaf-Curl-Virus	700	150	150	1000
Bacterial Spot	700	150	150	1000
Healthy	700	150	150	1000
Total Datasets				= 10,000

Table 5: Dataset of Tomato Plant Disease Detection and classification (60%, 20%, 20%)

<i>Class or Category</i>	<i>No. of Training images</i>	<i>No. of Validation images</i>	<i>No. of Test images</i>	<i>Total images</i>
Early Blight	600	200	200	1000
Late Blight	600	200	200	1000
Leaf Mold	600	200	200	1000
Septorial-Leaf-Spot	600	200	200	1000
Spider-Mites (Two-spotted-Spider-Mite)	600	200	200	1000
Target Spot	600	200	200	1000
Mosaic Virus	600	200	200	1000
Yellow-Leaf-Curl-Virus	600	200	200	1000
Bacterial Spot	600	200	200	1000
Healthy	600	200	200	1000
Total Datasets				= 10,000

A) Training Data (Image)

Training data (or a training dataset) is the initial data which uses to train deep learning models. Training datasets are feed to deep learning algorithms to teach them how to make predictions or perform a desired task.

B) Validation Data (Image)

The validation data set provides an unbiased evaluation of a model fit on the training data set while tuning the model's hyper parameters. Validation datasets can be used for regularization by early stopping (stopping training when the error on the validation data set increases, as this is a sign of over-fitting to the training data set). We were also to use validation dataset to compare different pre-trained models to select the most top 5 models. Depending on the accuracy value, the model that had highest accuracy value have been selected and used in this study.

C) Test Data (Image)

The test data set is a data set used to provide an unbiased evaluation of a final model fit on the training data set. If the data in the test data set has never been used in training (for example in cross-validation), the test data set is also called a holdout data set.

3.6.2 Image Augmentation

Data augmentation is a technique that can be used to artificially expand the size of a training set by creating modified data from the existing one. It is a good practice to use Data Augmentation to prevent over fitting, or the initial dataset is too small to train on, or even if you want to squeeze better performance from your model. Since we collected smaller dataset from farm fields, we can make up for it by augmenting this dataset and increasing our dataset size. Example for each disease type only 200 images had been collected from farm field (total collected images for ten classes = 2000). By using augmentation techniques, we make up 1000 images for each class, so total images used in the study were = 10,000. We apply various changes to the initial data: Geometric transformations - you can randomly flip, crop, rotate or translate images. To augment images when using Tensor Flow or Keras as our DL framework, we can:

- ✓ Write our own augmentation pipelines or layers.
- ✓ Use Keras preprocessing layers
- ✓ Use Image Data Generator

Some of the standard image augmentation techniques used include:

- a. Rotating an image by a given angle
- b. Flipping an image horizontally
- c. Shear range with some value
- d. Scaling image inwards or outwards for different degrees of zoom
- e. Shift range (horizontal and vertical) with some values, etc.

```
#Data Augmentation
from keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
import numpy as np
import os
from PIL import Image
from skimage import io
datagen = ImageDataGenerator(
    rotation_range=40,
    width_shift_range=0.2,
    height_shift_range=0.2,
    rescale=1./255,
    shear_range=0.2,
    zoom_range=0.2,
    horizontal_flip=True,
    fill_mode='reflect')

i = 0
for batch in datagen.flow_from_directory(directory='C:/Users/.
    batch_size = 40,
    target_size = (256,256),
    color_mode='rgb',
    save_to_dir='C:/Users/Abay
    save_prefix="aug_TOM_TS",
    save_format='jpg'):

    i += 1
    if i >= 15:
        break
```

Figure 6: Data augmentation techniques

Table 6: Image Augmentation using single original sample image

3.6.3 Disease Detection

Plant diseases and pest's detection is a very important research content in the field of computer vision. It is a technology that uses computer vision equipment to acquire images to judge whether there are diseases and pests in the collected plant images (tomato images). We had developed real time tomato leaf disease detection and classification model (TFLite). This model is compatible with smart phones, tablets and any computers.

3.7 Materials and Tools

3.7.1 Hardware Tools

- A) Camera: it is used for capturing image of various tomato leaves (diseases and healthy).
- B) Personal computer (Laptop), with Intel (R) Core (TM) i5-4210M CPU@2.60GHz, RAM: 8.0 GB, Window 11 Enterprise LTSC, 64-bit Operating system ,64x-based processor.
- C) AWS Cloud storage (for Web application or TFLite model)

3.7.2 Software Tools

A) Python

Python is an open source programming language. It was made to be easy-to-read and powerful. A Dutch programmer named Guido van Rossum made Python in 1991. He named it after the television program Monty Python's Flying Circus. Python is an interpreted language. Interpreted languages do not need to be compiled to run. A program called an interpreter runs Python code on almost any kind of computer. This means that a programmer can change the code and quickly see the results. This also means Python is slower than a compiled language like C, because it is not running machine code directly.

Python is a good programming language for beginners. It is a high-level language, which means a programmer can focus on what to do, but does not require knowledge of computer hardware. Writing programs in Python takes less time than in some other languages. Python drew inspiration from other programming languages like C, C++, Java, Perl, and Lisp.

B) Keras library

Keras is a high-level, deep learning API developed by Google for implementing neural networks. It is written in Python and is used to make the implementation of neural networks easy. It also supports multiple backend neural network computation. Keras is relatively easy to learn and work with because it provides a python frontend with a high level of abstraction while having the option of multiple back-ends for computation purposes. This makes Keras slower than other deep learning frameworks, but extremely beginner-friendly. Keras package of python is used for image processing purposes. (Keras is the most used deep learning framework. Keras is used for creating deep models which can be productized on smartphones.

- Keras is also used for distributed training of deep learning models and it is used by companies such as Netflix, Yelp, Uber, etc.
- Keras is also extensively used in deep learning competitions to create and deploy working models, which are fast in a short amount of time.
- Keras best runs on GPUs and TPUs.
- Keras is known for its fast computation, user-friendliness and ease of access.)

C) Tensor Flow Python

Tensor Flow is free and open source application which is one of the famous deep learning frameworks, developed by Google Team. Tensor Flow is a popular framework of machine learning and deep learning. It is released on 9 November 2015 and developed by Google Brain Team. It is entirely based on Python programming language and use for numerical computation and data flow, which makes machine learning faster and easier.

Tensor Flow can train and run the deep neural networks for image recognition, handwritten digit classification, recurrent neural network, word embedding, natural language processing, video detection, and many more. Tensor Flow is run on multiple CPUs or GPUs and also mobile operating systems. The name Tensor Flow is derived from its core framework, "Tensor." A tensor is a vector or a matrix of n-dimensional that represents all type of data. All values in a tensor hold similar data type with a known shape. The shape of the data is the dimension of the matrix or an array. A tensor can be generated from

the input data or the result of a computation. In Tensor Flow, all operations are conducted inside a graph. The group is a set of calculation that takes place successively. Each transaction is called an op node are connected.

D) Microsoft Visio 2016

Visio 2016 is used for designing the system architecture. This tool was used to design a diagram and to create a Gant chart easily with ready-made templates and helping to simplify complex information.

E) Google Collab:

Collaborator, or “Collab” for short, is a product from Google Research. Collab allows anybody to write and execute arbitrary python code through the browser. More technically, Collab is a hosted Jupiter notebook service that requires no setup to use, while providing access free of charge to computing resources including GPUs and TPU. Google Collab Has a huge library for machine learning, deep learning, and data science.

F) Mendeley:

Mendeley is Desktop software that is used as a PDF reader and also helps to easily cite documents with desired formats like IEEE, APA, and others. Mendeley automatically loads all information that is used for citation, unlike Microsoft Word which takes time and effort to fill all the information, because of this; it’s a great tool for researchers. It has a plugin that can be synchronized with Microsoft Word.

Table 7 : Tools and Python Libraries (open source)

3.8 Regularizing Techniques

Regularization is a technique which makes slight modifications to the learning algorithm such that the model generalizes better. This in turn improves the model's performance on the unseen data as well. Tikhonov regularization, along with principal component regression and many other regularization schemes, fall under the umbrella of spectral regularization, regularization characterized by the application of a filter.

3.8.1 Dropout

Dropout is a technique where randomly selected neurons are ignored during training. They are “dropped-out” randomly. This means that their contribution to the activation of downstream neurons is temporally removed on the forward pass and any weight updates are not applied to the neuron on the backward pass. As a neural network learns, neuron weights settle into their context within the network. Weights of neurons are tuned for specific features providing some specialization. Neighboring neurons become to rely on this specialization, which if taken too far can result in a fragile model too specialized to the training data. This reliant on context for a neuron during training is referred to complex co-adaptations. You can imagine that if neurons are randomly dropped out of the network during training that other neurons will have to step in and handle the representation required to make predictions for the missing neurons. This is believed to result in multiple independent internal representations being learned by the network. The effect is that the network becomes less sensitive to the specific weights of neurons. This in turn results in a network that is capable of better generalization and is less likely to over fit the training data.

3.8.2 Early Stopping

Early stopping is a form of regularization used to avoid over fitting when training a learner with an iterative method, such as gradient descent. Such methods update the learner so as to make it better fit the training data with each iteration. Up to a point, this improves the learner's performance on data outside of the training set. Early stopping rules provide guidance as to how many iterations can be run before the learner begins to over-fit.

3.9 Optimizing Algorithms

An optimization algorithm finds the value of the parameters (weights) that minimize the error when mapping inputs to outputs. While training the deep learning model, we need to modify each epoch's weights and minimize the loss function. An optimizer is a function or an algorithm that modifies the

attributes of the neural network, such as weights and learning rate. Thus, it helps in reducing the overall loss and improves the accuracy. Here in the study we had used Adam for learning rate.

3.10 Evaluation Metrics:

3.10.1 F1 Score:

The F1-score combines the precision and recall of a classifier into a single metric by taking their harmonic mean. It is primarily used to compare the performance of two classifiers. Suppose that classifier A has a higher recall, and classifier B has higher precision. The F1-score of a classification model is calculated as follows:

Equation 1: Calculating F1-Score

$$\text{F 1 Score} = \frac{2(P * R)}{P + R}$$

Where as , P = the precision R = the recall

3.10.2 Recall:

The recall is calculated as the ratio between the numbers of Positive samples correctly classified as Positive to the total number of Positive samples. The recall measures the model's ability to detect Positive samples. The higher the recall, the more positive samples detected. Recall (or True Positive Rate) is calculated by dividing the true positives by anything that should have been predicted as positive.

Equation 2: Calculating Recall

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

3.10.3 Precision:

Precision is one indicator of a deep learning model's performance – the quality of a positive prediction made by the model. Precision refers to the number of true positives divided by the total number of positive predictions (i.e., the number of true positives plus the number of false positives).

Equation 3: Calculating Precision

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positive}}$$

3.10.4 Accuracy of Classification

Accuracy is a metric that generally describes how the model performs across all classes. It is useful when all classes are of equal importance. It is calculated as the ratio between the numbers of correct predictions to the total number of predictions.

Equation 4: Calculating Accuracy

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{True Positives} + \text{True Negatives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{True Negatives} + \text{False Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

		Predicted Value	
		Positive	Negative
Actual Value	Positive	True Positive	False Negative
	Negative	False Positive	True Negative

Figure 7: Confusion Matrix

- Top-Left (True Positive): How many times did the model correctly classify a Positive sample as Positive?
- Top-Right (False Negative): How many times did the model incorrectly classify a Positive sample as Negative?
- Bottom-Left (False Positive): How many times did the model incorrectly classify a Negative sample as Positive?

- Bottom-Right (True Negative): How many times did the model correctly classify a Negative sample as Negative?

3.11 Performance Measurement

3.11.1 Cross-Entropy

Cross entropy loss is a metric used to measure how well a classification model in deep learning performs. The loss (or error) is measured as a number between 0 and 1, with 0 being a perfect model. The goal is generally to get your model as close to 0 as possible. Cross-entropy loss is used when adjusting model weights during training. The aim is to minimize the loss, i.e., the smaller the loss the better the model

3.11.2 Loss Function

The most popular loss functions for deep learning classification models are **binary** cross-entropy and **sparse** categorical cross-entropy. Binary cross-entropy is useful for binary and multi label classification problems. So here we are using binary cross-entropy for our Research.

Chapter Four: Research Design and Implementation

4.1 Introduction

The process in which tomato plant leaf diseases Detection and classification are defined in Design and Development part of the research. In this research Python integrated with tensor flow and keras package are used. In the Diseases Detection and classification process, images are captured by digital camera or smart phones then, the captured images are used to identify the affected area of leaf after image processing. Web application was developed to detect tomato leaf disease at real time in farm field by using smart phone and internet.

4.2 Implementation Environment

In this study we had implemented the selected pre-trained models on python programming language (3.9.6) with addition of Jupiter notebook as simulation tools or IDE (integrated development environment). Python language is simple and interactive language that also had wide online support forum, so we choose. The simulation part of the research is deployed and experimented on Collab to use GPU for fast run and more experimentation on different baselines. We had also used Amazon Cloud service (AWS) for web application deployment as it predict the tomato leaf disease at real time from farm filed using smart phone and internet (to connect to cloud model). For Web app development we had used python, flask, HTML and CSS, tools.

Figure 8: General Architecture of the Pre-trained Models.

4.3 Model Selection

Model selection is the task of selecting a model from among various candidates on the basis of performance criterion to choose the best one.[48] In the context of learning, this may be the selection of models from a set of candidate models (Model dictionary), given data. In the simplest cases, a pre-existing set of data is considered. However, the task can also involve the design of experiments such that the data collected is well-suited to the problem of model selection. Given candidate models of similar predictive or explanatory power, the simplest model is most likely to be the best choice. In its most basic forms, model selection is one of the fundamental tasks of scientific inquiry. Determining the principle that explains a series of observations is often linked directly to a mathematical model predicting those observations.

We had selected our model from model Dictionary that found on keras application. This dictionary contains more than 25 models which are pre-trained with different number of datasets. After executing the Model Dictionary on Jupiter notebook simulation, we had selected top five models for our research. These models are Restnet152V2, MobilenetV2, InceptionV3, EfficientnetB3 and CNN and TFLite model was extracted from CNN model for real time tomato disease detection and classification (web app) purpose. This collection of models (Dictionary with Models) is shown below.

```

# Dictionary with the models
models = {
    "DenseNet121": {"model":tf.keras.applications.DenseNet121, "perf":0},
    "MobileNetV2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV2, "perf":0},
    "DenseNet169": {"model":tf.keras.applications.DenseNet169, "perf":0},
    "DenseNet201": {"model":tf.keras.applications.DenseNet201, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB0": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB0, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB1": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB1, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB2, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB3": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB3, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB4": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB4, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB5": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB4, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB6": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB4, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB7": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB4, "perf":0},
    "InceptionResNetV2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.InceptionResNetV2, "perf":0},
    "InceptionV3": {"model":tf.keras.applications.InceptionV3, "perf":0},
    "MobileNet": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNet, "perf":0},
    "MobileNetV2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV2, "perf":0},
    "MobileNetV3Large": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV3Large, "perf":0},
    "MobileNetV3Small": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV3Small, "perf":0},
    "NASNetMobile": {"model":tf.keras.applications.NASNetMobile, "perf":0},
    "ResNet101": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet101, "perf":0},
    "ResNet101V2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet101V2, "perf":0},
    "ResNet152": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet152, "perf":0},
    "ResNet152V2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet152V2, "perf":0},
    "ResNet50": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet50, "perf":0},
    "ResNet50V2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet50V2, "perf":0},
    "VGG16": {"model":tf.keras.applications.VGG16, "perf":0},
    "VGG19": {"model":tf.keras.applications.VGG19, "perf":0},
    "Xception": {"model":tf.keras.applications.Xception, "perf":0}
}

```

Figure 9: Dictionary with Pre-trained models (Models pack)

Figure 10: Test accuracy of pre-trained models in Dictionary with models (after 1 epoch)

Figure 11: Running time of Pre-trained Models in Dictionary with models.

4.4 System Architecture of the Selected Pre-trained Models

In this study we had discussed the system architecture of selected pre-trained models that used for the tomato leaf disease detection and classification. We have discussed here only the system architecture of selected pre-trained models.

4.4.1 MobilenetV2

MobileNetV2 is a convolutional neural network architecture that seeks to perform well on mobile devices. It is based on an inverted residual structure where the residual connections are between the bottleneck layers. MobileNet is a deep learning architecture that focuses on the mobile platform where the computational resource is limited.[30] MobileNetV2 is an improvement over MobileNetV1. Both of them still retain separable convolution as the core layer, where the number of parameters trained is much reduced compared to the full convolutional. The small requirement of the parameter number allows MobileNetV2 suitable for mobile phone applications, where the number of registers is much less compared to desktop.

Figure 12: MobilenetV2 Architecture .taken from [33]

4.4.2 Restnet152v2

Residual Neural Network (ResNet152V2) is a convolutional neural network which has 152 layers in it. To solve the problem of vanishing gradients ResNet uses skip connection for fitting the output from previous layer to next layer. It has been the winner Image Net challenge in 2015. It is used to compare the accuracy of the other selected pre-trained models. It is a pre-trained model that has several convolution layers and max pooling layers. Arguments of the ResNet function are include top, weights, input tensor, input shape, pooling, classes, classifier activation.[49]

Figure 13: Restnet152V2 Architecture, taken from[28]

4.4.3 CNN

Convolution neural networks are one of the most important components of neural networks (CNN)[50]. It contains neurons with varying degrees of learning and bias. Before transferring the activation, function and responding to the output, each neuron receives a weighted sum of multiple inputs. The three most commonly used layers on CNN are the flexible layer, the integration layer, and the dense layer (Fully Connected Nerve Network). The structure of pre-trained model (CNN) is shown below.

Figure 14: CNN Architecture, taken from[31]

4.4.4 Inception V3

Inception-v3 is a pre-trained convolutional neural network model that is 48 layers deep. It is a version of the network already trained on more than a million images from the Image Net database. It is the third edition of Inception CNN model by Google, originally instigated during the Image Net Recognition Challenge.

Figure 15: Inception V3 Architecture, taken from[44]

4.4.5 Efficientnetb3

EfficientNet is convolutional neural network architecture and scaling method that uniformly scales all dimensions of depth/width/resolution using a compound coefficient. Unlike conventional practice that arbitrary scales these factors, the EfficientNet scaling method uniformly scales network width, depth, and resolution with a set of fixed scaling coefficients. The compound scaling method is justified by the intuition that if the input image is bigger, then the network needs more layers to increase the receptive field and more channels to capture more fine-grained patterns on the bigger image. [39]

Figure 16: Architecture of efficientnetB3, taken from[39]

4.5 System Architecture of the Developed Web app (TFLite Model)

Real-Time Image Detection is a computer vision task that involves shooting (taking) images by using phone camera in the farm field and uploading to Web app (TFLite model) to detect whether the leaf image is affected or not affected. Using either the TFJS Task API or the TFLITE Web API it is possible to deploy Tensor flow Lite models on the web without even needing to convert them into Tensorflow.js format.[51] After the deployment of TFLite model to the cloud the customer use the IP or URL (Uniform Resource Locator) to connect the UI of the Web app that contain the TFLite model. After once connected to UI the customer capture leaf image from farm filed and uploads to Web app on the cloud. Finally, the TFLite model detects the leaf image to predict whether the leaf is affected or healthy. The Web app then links the predicted value from TFLite model to web page that contains recommendation or chemical treatment of plant leaf disease. Finally, the predicted value and recommendation of the treatment is concatenated and displayed for user on UI. The system architecture of Web app is shown below:-

Figure 17: Web App Architecture with TFLite model.

4.3 Experimental Setup

The experimental setup of this study includes five scenarios to efficiently detect at real time the tomato plant diseases. The first scenario is collecting the dataset from different farm field with help of farm expert (pathogens expert) that had farm telescope. The second scenario is downloading the deep learning pre-trained models from keras application (which is model dictionary) and import to python codes that evaluate the performance of each model in the collection. The third scenario is selecting best five models that have highest training and validation accuracy. The fourth Scenario is training the selected top five models one by one on simulation environment and evaluates all training, validation and test accuracy. The fifth scenario is developing or deriving TFLite model from CNN model for real time tomato leaf disease

detection and classification. And also experimenting pre-trained model and TFLite model with different hyper parameters (like batch size, epoch, optimizer, loss function, etc.).

4.5.1 Augmentation Parameter

Deep Learning has millions of parameters, to build robust model massive number of datasets is required, which is difficult to get all at once from farm filed. If we use insufficient data the model fails in to over fitting. To solve this problem data augmentation is the best solution. Augmentation is mentioned on section 3.5.2

```
datagen = ImageDataGenerator(
    rotation_range=40,
    width_shift_range=0.2,
    height_shift_range=0.2,
    rescale=1./255,
    shear_range=0.2,
    zoom_range=0.2,
    horizontal_flip=True,
    fill_mode='reflect')
```

Figure 18: Image Augmentation Python code

4.5.2 Hyper Parameter Tuning

Hyper parameters are the variable that used in deep neural network models building and evaluation process. In this study we had used different hyper parameters to evaluate and select the top five models from the Model dictionary and used to the measure performance of the selected models. We have made different experimentation on the selected models by changing the hyper parameters value. The following hyper parameters are used in the study:

A. Optimization Algorithm

To train the deep neural network an optimization algorithm is plays a major because it allows a model to learn faster and achieve better performance. There are many types of optimization algorithms from those we had used Adam. We experiment on the learning rate of 0.0001 and 0.001. Learning rate is the amount of weight update during training. It is configurable and ranges between 0 and 1. Learning rate is the most important hyper parameter, because of it controls how fast a model adapts to a given problem.

B. Loss Function (cost function)

Loss function is a method of evaluating how well the algorithm is on parameters. If the predictions are totally off, the loss function will output a higher number. If the model is pretty good, it will output a lower number. As we tune our algorithm to try and improve the model, loss function will tell us if we are improving or not. Loss helps us to understand how much the predicted value differs from actual value. There are many types of loss function, but we are using Binary classification entropy. Binary classification is a prediction algorithm where the output can be either one of two items, indicated by 0 or 1. The output of binary classification algorithms is a prediction score (mostly). So, the classification happens based on the threshold the value (default value is 0.5). If the prediction score > threshold then 1 else 0. Binary cross entropy measures how far away from the true value (which is either 0 or 1) the prediction is for each of the classes and then averages these class-wise errors to obtain the final loss. We can define cross entropy as the difference between two probability distributions p and q, where p is our true output and q is our estimate of this true output. This difference is now applied to our neural networks, where it is extremely effective because of their strong usage of probability.

Equation 5: formula to calculate probability of Loss

$$H(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N \overset{\text{true label}}{p(x)} \log \overset{\text{estimate}}{q(x)}$$

Where H(x) = loss function

N = number of class or category

P = actual value (true label)

Q = predicted value (estimated value)

C. Epoch

It describes the number of the times the training data shown to the deep learning network. During experimentation as a baseline, the number of epochs taken was 20 and for interpreting different pre-trained models we had used different epoch numbers.

D. Batch Size

The batch size is a hyper parameter that defines the number of samples to work through before updating the internal model parameters. At the end of the batch, the predictions are compared to the expected output variables and an error is calculated. From this error, the update algorithm is used to improve the model.

E. Activation Function

After each convolution layer the trained models used non-linear activation function called RELU. Although it gives an impression of a linear function, ReLU has a derivative function and allows for back

propagation while simultaneously making it computationally efficient. The main catch here is that the ReLU function does not activate all the neurons at the same time. The neurons will only be deactivated if the output of the linear transformation is less than 0. An Activation Function decides whether a neuron should be activated or not. This means that it will decide whether the neuron's input to the network is important or not in the process of prediction using simpler mathematical operations.

Equation 6: formula for Activation function

$$f(x) = \max(0, x)$$

At the output layer of the models used in this study, we had used Soft Max activation function.

4.4 Tomato Leave Diseases Detection using Pre-trained Models

Image processing techniques is the best solution for plant leaf disease detection. Its capability of automatically feature extraction makes it the best solution for plant leaf disease detection. On some article it is stated that researchers prefer to use deep learning algorithm rather than traditional machine learning methods that used manual feature extraction. Here is the architecture of the selected pre-trained models.

Figure 19: General System Architecture of the study

4.5 Real-Time Tomato Leaf Diseases Detection and classification using TFLite

4.5.1 Tensor Flow Lite

Tensor Flow Lite, often referred to as TFLite, is an open source library developed by Google for deploying deep learning models to edge devices. Tensor Flow Lite is a set of tools that enables on-device deep learning by helping developers run their models on mobile, embedded, and edge devices. We can use TFLite for natural language processing, computer vision, or any machine learning model you build in Tensor Flow. Tensor Flow Lite allows us to convert a Tensor Flow model (using Tensor Flow Lite

Converter) to get a .tflite file and then load that file on your device. When using TFLite for computer vision, you are able to do on-device inference for things like image classification or object detection.

4.5.2 TFLite Web API

The TFLite Web API allows users to run arbitrary TFLite models on the web. Users can load a TFLite model from a URL, use TFJS tensors to set the model's input data, run inference, and get the output back in TFJS tensors. Furthermore, the library also includes some helper classes that help with certain model types like image Detection models. To develop the TFLite model we had used pre-trained deep learning model which is CNN and drive this mode by using Quantization techniques. After quantization we load the lightweight TFLite model and train once again. We also evaluate TFLite model with test dataset and check the accuracy of the model. Finally, we had integrated the TFLite model to flask to develop the Web App that can be hosted to AWS cloud and used for Real Time tomato leaf disease detection and classification at real time from farm field by using smart phone and internet.

4.5.3 Run Inference (Execute TFLite Model)

After converting CNN TF Model to TFLite model, we had executed the TFLite model in order to predict the target class, which is known as inference the model. Inference refers to the process of executing a TFLite model on-device to make predictions based on input data. There is different way of inference based on model type, but in this study, we had used Model without metadata.

A) Models without metadata:

Use the Tensor Flow Lite Interpreter API Supported on multiple platforms and languages such as Java, Swift, C++, Objective-C and Python.

B) Models with metadata:

You can either leverage the out-of-box APIs using the Tensor Flow Lite Task Library or build custom inference pipelines with the Tensor Flow Lite Support Library. On android devices, users can automatically generate code wrappers using the Android Studio ML Model Binding or the Tensor Flow

C) Lite Code Generator. Supported only by Java (Android) while Swift (iOS) and C++ is work in progress. On Android and iOS devices, you can improve performance using hardware acceleration. On either platform you can use a GPU Delegate, on android you can either use the NNAPI Delegate (for newer devices) or the Hexagon Delegate (on older devices) and on iOS you can use the Core ML Delegate.

4.5.4 Create Template (Web Page)

In this study to recommend the chemical treatment to cure the affected plant leaves, we had made link between the prediction output and template (web page) that hold the full information about disease and its remedy. To do this we had made template (web page) for each class (category) and this webpage hold full information about each disease and its remedy. This web page has also hyperlinked to main website that found in US. The main website which found in US has all information about all tomato leave disease with its remedy and it act as the main pathogenic disease system. The website is hosted by Clemson University as Clemson University Cooperative Extension Service. The author develops the templates by using HTML, CSS, JavaScript and Bootstraps. The templates are shown below.

Figure 20: Template (web page) for all Classes

4.5.5 Develop Flask app (Web app)

Flask is a web framework, which provides tools, libraries and technologies that allow us to build a web application. The web application can be some web pages or website. We have developed Web app using flask framework on Python programming language. After developing web app how to integrate TFLite model and templates to it, to predict the disease and give recommendation?

- TFLite model was loaded in to the web app by calling its directory path in to the web app.
- Templates also integrated with web app by concatenating the label of the class with respective template by using if, else condition. The template contains full information about its label class, including the recommendation and chemical treatment.

- Once the flask app or web app run (inference) on cloud on the backend side, it works the prediction on front side till the developer stop running web app on cloud. So, frontend user(customer) can use the home page of the web app to upload the image directly from farm field and press predict button to get the predicted output by the web app. Internet connection is needed at farm filed on the customer smartphone to do this task. For inference (run) web app on cloud, interpreter is used, which is called TFLite API.
- The flask app forwards the prediction output and corresponding template to the customer (browser) by concatenating the prediction output and corresponding template (web page), to do this the web app use web tensor called TFJS.
- Finally, the customers use the information from the web app in his/her smartphone and take measurement to tackle the spread of disease or to cure plant.

4.5.6 Deploy TFLite Model to AWS Cloud

Tools in TFLite are used to deploy Web app to cloud. After the deployment of TFLite model to the cloud, the customer uses the IP address or web address to connect to the Web app that contains the TFLite model. After once connected to TFJS tensor the customer can input data (upload the tomato leaf image tomato) from farm filed and click predict button. Finally, the TFLite model detects the leaf image to predict whether the leaf is affected or healthy. The Web app then display the predicted value from TFLite model by concatenating the output with the corresponding template (Recommendation). Finally, the predicted value with recommendation or chemical treatment is displayed for user on UI.

The GUI of Web app is shown below.

Figure 21: Home page of web app for Real time Tomato disease detection and prediction on AWS Cloud.

Chapter Five: Result and Discussion

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter we discussed the result of selected models and web app prediction. This chapter includes experimental result of different models and the experimental result of TFLite model which is used on smart phone to detect and predict tomato leaf disease at real time from farm field. The comparison of each implemented Pre-trained models also discussed depending on different hyper parameters.

5.2 Experimental Results

The image color that used for this study was RGB which shows the symptom of the disease clearly while we are seeing by farm telescope. Since we were used different pre-trained models for disease detection the size of image is different from model to model. But the range are: (256,256,3), (224,224,3), (32,32,3)). Selected pre-trained models were Restnet152V2, MobilenetV2, Inception V3, efficientnetb3, CNN and TFLite model for Web App and Mobile App. These pre-trained models are selected depending on their performance by evaluating the models using hyper parameters. The model selection is discussed under section 4.2.

5.2.1 Experimental Result of Restnet152V2

As we had discussed on section 4.3 from selected pre-trained models resnet152v2 is one which predict remarkable result while using our datasets that have been collected from different farm field. This model used image size of 224*224*3. The model trained with 6000 tomato leaf images and validated with 2000 tomato leaf images and tested with 2000 tomato leaf images basically, but as our dataset split in to 3 (60:20:20 or 70:15:15 or 80:10:10) different ratio the training, validation and testing images number may vary. Different experimentation is takes place on this model during training and testing process. This experimentation is conducted based on different hyper parameters, like different batch number, learning rate, epoch, activation function and etc. The training and validation graph and other experimentation result are shown below:

Figure 22: Restnet152v2 model, Train and Validation (accuracy and loss) Graph

- The above graph (Restnet152V2 graph) can be interpreted(analyze) as the following:
- The training and validation (accuracy and loss) demonstrated well.
- As the number of the epoch increases the value of loss in both training and validation graph decreases which indicates the best performance approach of the mode during training.
- The best epoch that has minimum validation loss was epoch 10.
- As the number of epochs increases the value of accuracy also increases which indicates the training of the model is going well.
- The best accuracy epoch is epoch 4, that have highest validation accuracy value.

```

20/20 [=====] - 6s 283ms/step - loss: 0.2842 - accuracy: 0.9950
20/20 [=====] - 6s 279ms/step - loss: 0.2910 - accuracy: 0.9937
20/20 [=====] - 12s 464ms/step - loss: 0.2844 - accuracy: 0.9943
Train Loss: 0.28420647978782654
Train Accuracy Restnetv2: 0.9950000047683716
-----
Validation Loss: 0.2910044193267822
Validation Accuracy Restnetv2: 0.9937499761581421
-----
Test Loss: 0.28440821170806885
Test Accuracy Restnetv2: 0.9942857027053833

```

Figure 23: Restnet152v2 Train, Valid and Test (accuracy and loss) Result

- The above figure (23) indicates the experimentation output of training, validation and test of Restnet152V2 model during the training and test process. Hence the all experimentation output indicates the mode performs well.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
BS	1.00	1.00	1.00	140
EB	0.99	1.00	1.00	140
LB	1.00	0.99	0.99	140
LM	1.00	0.99	1.00	140
SLS	0.99	1.00	1.00	140
TSSM	1.00	0.99	1.00	140
TS	1.00	0.97	0.99	140
YLCV	1.00	1.00	1.00	140
MV	0.97	1.00	0.98	140
Healthy	0.99	1.00	1.00	140
accuracy			0.99	1400
macro avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	1400
weighted avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	1400

Figure 24: Restnet152 V2 Performance Evaluation Metrics Result

- The above figure (fig.24) show as the output values of evaluation metrics that used to evaluate the Restnet152V2 model during the model training.
- The graph indicates output value of evaluation metrics for all ten classes and the number of images used during the training.
- It also indicates the average value of the evaluation metrics.

Figure 25: Restnet152V2 Confusion Matrix Graph

- As it indicated on the confusion matrix above (Confusion matrix for Restnet152V2) the true label indicates the input while predicted label indicates the output.
- The diagonal line indicates the true positive value which means the model predict the input images as true and it was true.
- E.g. the Restnet152V2 model accepts 140 images as BS (bacterial spot) and predicts all 140 images as BS (bacterial spot).

```

Downloading data from https://storage.googleapis.com/tensorflow/keras-applications/resnet/resnet152v2_weights_tf_dim_ordering_t
f_kernels_notop.h5
234545216/234545216 [=====] - 7s 0us/step
Model: "sequential_1"
-----
Layer (type)                Output Shape                Param #
-----
resnet152v2 (Functional)    (None, 2048)                58331648
batch_normalization_95 (Bat (None, 2048)                8192
chNormalization)
dense_2 (Dense)              (None, 256)                 524544
dropout_1 (Dropout)         (None, 256)                 0
dense_3 (Dense)              (None, 10)                  2570
-----
Total params: 58,866,954
Trainable params: 58,719,114
Non-trainable params: 147,840
-----

```

Figure 26: Resnet152V2 Structure

5.2.2 Experimental Result of MobilenetV2

Mobilnetv2 model is one of pre-trained model in Dictionary with models in keras application and selected as one of top 5 models for this study. Mobilnetv2 gave us promising result when we train it using our collected dataset. This model accepts image size of 224*224*3. The model trained with 6000 tomato leaf images and validated with 2000 tomato leaf images and tested with 2000 tomato leaf images basically, but as our dataset split in to 3 (60:20:20 or 70:15:15 or 80:10:10) different ratio the training, validation and testing images number may vary. Different experimentation is takes place on this model during training and testing process. This experimentation is conducted based on different hyper parameters, like different batch number, learning rate, epoch, activation function and etc. The training and validation graph and other experimentation result are shown below:

Figure 27: MobilenetV2 Training and Validation (accuracy and loss) Graph

The above graph (MobilenetV2 graph) can be interpreted (analyzed) as the following:

- The training and validation (accuracy and loss) demonstrated well.
- As the number of the epoch increases the value of loss in both training and validation graph decreases which indicates the best performance approach of the mode during training.
- The best epoch that has minimum validation loss was epoch 9.
- As the number of epochs increases the value of accuracy also increases which indicates the training of the model is going well.
- The best accuracy epoch is epoch 9, that have highest validation accuracy value.

```

Train Loss: 0.3324621915817261
Train Accuracy MobileNetV2: 0.9863560795783997
-----
Validation Loss: 0.3294104337692261
Validation Accuracy MobileNetV2: 0.9875208139419556
-----
Test Loss: 0.34027913212776184
Test Accuracy MobileNetV2: 0.9833610653877258

```

Figure 28: MobilenetV2 Train, Valid and Test (accuracy and loss) Result

- The above figure (figure 28) indicates the experimentation output of training, validation and test of MobilenetV2 model during the training and test process. Hence all the experimentation output indicates that the mode performs well.

- All training, validation and test loss value is between 1 and 0 and precise to 0 which indicates the model performance very good.
- All training, validation and test accuracy of the model close to 100, which mean great and high model performance.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
BS	0.97	0.93	0.95	120
EB	1.00	0.97	0.99	120
LB	1.00	0.93	0.96	120
LM	0.98	1.00	0.99	120
SLS	1.00	1.00	1.00	120
TSSM	1.00	1.00	1.00	120
TS	0.95	1.00	0.98	120
YLCV	0.98	1.00	0.99	120
MV	0.96	1.00	0.98	120
Healthy	0.98	1.00	0.99	120
accuracy			0.98	1202
macro avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	1202
weighted avg	0.98	0.98	0.98	1202

Figure 29: MobilenetV2 Performance Evaluation Metrics Experimentation Result

- The above figure (fig.29) show as the output values of evaluation metrics that used to evaluate the MobilenetV2 model during the model training.
- The graph indicates output value of evaluation metrics for all ten categories and the number of images (support) used during the training.
- It also indicates the average value of the evaluation metrics.

Figure 30: MobulenetV2 Confusion Matrix

- As it indicated on the confusion matrix above (Confusion matrix for MobulenetV2) the true label indicates the input while predicted label indicates the output.
- The diagonal line indicates the true positive value which means the model predict the input images as true and it was true.
- E.g. the MobulenetV2 model accepts 162 images as Healthy and predicts all 162 images as Healthy.

```

Downloading data from https://storage.googleapis.com/tensorflow/keras-applications/mobilenet_v2/mobilenet_v2_weights_tf_dim_ordering_tf_kernels_1.0_224_no_top.h5
9406464/9406464 [=====] - 0s 0us/step
Model: "sequential"
-----
Layer (type)                Output Shape              Param #
-----
mobilenetv2_1.00_224 (Func  (None, 1280)             2257984
tional)

batch_normalization (Batch  (None, 1280)             5120
normalization)

dense (Dense)                (None, 256)              327936

dropout (Dropout)           (None, 256)              0

dense_1 (Dense)              (None, 10)               2570
-----
Total params: 2,593,610
Trainable params: 2,556,938
Non-trainable params: 36,672
-----

```

Figure 31: MobilenetV2 Structure

5.2.3 Experimental Result of InceptionV3

How pre-trained models are selected for this study had discussed on section 4.3. From selected pre-trained models InceptionV3 is one, which predicts remarkable result while using our datasets that have been collected from different farm field. This model used image size of 224*224*3. The model trained with 6000 tomato leaf images and validated with 2000 tomato leaf images and tested with 2000 tomato leaf images basically, but as our dataset split in to 3 (60:20:20 or 70:15:15 or 80:10:10) different ratio the training, validation and testing images number may vary. Different experimentation is takes place on this model during training and testing process. This experimentation is conducted based on different hyper parameters. By changing the number of hyper parameters like: batch number, learning rate, epoch, activation function and etc. The training and validation graph and other experimentation result are shown below:

Figure 32: InceptionV3 Training and Validation (accuracy and loss) Graph

- From above graph (InceptionV3 graph) we can analyze the training and validation (accuracy and loss) demonstrated with different color line and color full point.
- As the number of the epoch increases the value of loss in both training and validation graph decreases
- The best epoch that has minimum validation loss was epoch 10.
- As the number of epochs increases the value of accuracy also increases which indicates the training of the model is going well.
- The best accuracy epoch is epoch 5, that have highest validation accuracy value.

```

Train Loss:  0.3756001889705658
Train Accuracy:  0.9910149574279785
-----
Validation Loss:  0.3784111440181732
Validation Accuracy:  0.9889767169952393
-----
Test Loss:  0.3764601945877075
Test Accuracy:  0.9883527159690857

```

Figure 33: InceptionV3 Train, Valid and Test (accuracy and loss) Value

- The above figure (figure 33) indicates the experimentation output of training, validation and test of InceptionV3 model during the training and test experimentation. Hence all the experimentation output indicates that the mode performs well.
- All training, validation and test loss value is between 1 and 0 and precise to 0 which indicates the model performance is very good.

- All training, validation and test accuracy of the model close to 100, which mean great and high model performance.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
BS	1.00	0.92	0.96	122
EB	0.99	1.00	1.00	120
LB	0.98	0.99	0.98	120
LM	0.94	1.00	0.97	120
SLS	1.00	0.99	1.00	120
TSSM	1.00	1.00	1.00	120
TS	1.00	1.00	1.00	120
YLCV	1.00	0.99	1.00	120
MV	0.98	0.99	0.99	120
Healthy	1.00	1.00	1.00	120
accuracy			0.99	1202
macro avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	1202
weighted avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	1202

Figure 34: InceptionV3 Model Performance Evaluation Metrics Value

- The above figure (fig.34) show as the output values of evaluation metrics that used to evaluate the InceptionV3 model during the model training.
- The graph indicates output value of evaluation metrics for all ten categories and the number of images (support) used during the training.
- It also indicates the average value of the evaluation metrics.

Figure 35: InceptionV3 Confusion Matrix

- As it indicated on the confusion matrix above (Confusion matrix for Inception V3) the true label indicates the input while predicted label indicates the output (predicted value).
- The diagonal line indicates the **true positive** value which mean the model predict the input images as true and it was true.
- E.g. the Inception V3 model accepts 162 images as EB (Early Blight) and predicts all 162 images as EB (Early Blight).

```

model.summary()
Downloading data from https://storage.googleapis.com/tensorflow/keras-applications/inception_v3/inception_v3_weights_tf_dim_ordering_tf_kernels_notop.h5
87910968/87910968 [=====] - 3s 0us/step
Model: "sequential"
-----
Layer (type)                Output Shape                Param #
-----
inception_v3 (Functional)   (None, 2048)                21802784

batch_normalization_94 (Bat (None, 2048)                8192
chNormalization)

dense (Dense)                (None, 256)                 524544

dropout (Dropout)           (None, 256)                 0

dense_1 (Dense)              (None, 10)                  2570
-----
Total params: 22,338,090
Trainable params: 22,299,562
Non-trainable params: 38,528
-----

```

Figure 36: InceptionV3 Model Structure

5.2.4 Experimental Result of EfficientnetB3

Efficientnetb3 is one of the models that had satisfactory prediction result and which were selected from dictionary with models as we had discussed on section 4.3. This model used image size of 256*256*3. The model trained with 6000 tomato leaf images and validated with 2000 tomato leaf images and tested with 2000 tomato leaf images basically, but as our dataset split in to 3 (60:20:20 or 70:15:15 or 80:10:10) different ratio the training, validation and testing images number may vary. Different experimentation is takes place on this model during training and testing process. This experimentation is conducted based on different hyper parameters, like different batch number, learning rate, epoch, activation function and etc. The training and validation graph and other experimentation result are shown below:

Figure 37: EfficientnetB3 model, Train and Validation (accuracy and loss) Graph

- The above graph (EfficientnetB3 graph) can be interpreted(analyze) as the following:
- The training and validation (accuracy and loss) demonstrated well.
- As the number of the epoch increases the value of loss in both training and validation graph decreases which indicates the best performance approach of the mode during training.
- The best epoch that has minimum validation loss was epoch 10.
- As the number of epochs increases the value of accuracy also increases which indicates the training of the model is going well.
- The best accuracy epoch is epoch 8, that have highest validation accuracy value.

```

Train Loss: 0.19550356268882751
Train Accuracy EfficientNetB3: 0.9990741014480591
-----
Validation Loss: 0.19388923048973083
Validation Accuracy EfficientNetB3: 0.9990741014480591
-----
Test Loss: 0.1918836534023285
Test Accuracy EfficientNetB3: 1.0

```

Figure 38: EfficientnetB3 Model, Train, Valid and Test (accuracy and loss) Result

- The above figure (figure 38) indicates the experimentation output of training, validation and test of EfficientnetB3 model during the training and test experimentation. Hence all the experimentation output indicates that the mode performs well.

- All training, validation and test loss value is between 1 and 0 and precise to 0 which indicates the model performance is very good.
- All training, validation and test accuracy of the model close to 100, which mean great and high model performance.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
BS	1.00	1.00	1.00	162
EB	1.00	1.00	1.00	162
LB	1.00	1.00	1.00	162
LM	1.00	1.00	1.00	162
SLS	1.00	1.00	1.00	162
TSSM	1.00	1.00	1.00	162
TS	1.00	1.00	1.00	161
YLCV	1.00	1.00	1.00	161
MV	1.00	1.00	1.00	162
Healthy	1.00	1.00	1.00	162
accuracy			1.00	1618
macro avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	1618
weighted avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	1618

Figure 39: EfficientnetB3 Model Performance Evaluation Metrics Result

- The above figure (fig.39) show as the output values of evaluation metrics that used to evaluate the EfficientnetB3 model during the model training.
- The graph indicates output value of evaluation metrics for all ten categories and the number of images (support) used during the training.
- It also indicates the average value of the evaluation metrics.

Figure 40: EfficientnetB3 Model Confusion Matrix

- As it indicated on the confusion matrix above (Confusion matrix for EfficientnetB3) the true label indicates the input while predicted label indicates the output.
- The **diagonal** line indicates the **true positive** value which means the model predict the input images as true and it was true.
- E.g. the EfficientnetB3 model accepts 240 images as MV (Moistic Virus) and predicts all 240 images as MV (Moistic Virus).

Downloading data from https://storage.googleapis.com/keras-applications/efficientnetb3_notop.h5
 43941136/43941136 [=====] - 1s 0us/step
 Model: "sequential"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
efficientnetb3 (Functional)	(None, 1536)	10783535
batch_normalization (Batch Normalization)	(None, 1536)	6144
dense (Dense)	(None, 256)	393472
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 256)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 10)	2570
=====		
Total params: 11,185,721		
Trainable params: 11,095,346		
Non-trainable params: 90,375		

Figure 39: EfficientnetB3 Model Structure

5.2.5 Experimental Result of CNN

CNN is one of the models that used in this research and provide remarkable result while using our datasets that have been collected from different farm field. This model used image size of 224*224*3. This model is used as backbone model while we were testing dictionary with models to select best top 5 models for our research. The model trained with 6000 tomato leaf images and validated with 2000 tomato leaf images and tested with 2000 tomato leaf images basically, but as our dataset split in to 3 (60:20:20 or 70:15:15 or 80:10:10) different ratio the training, validation and testing images number may vary. Different experimentation is taken space on this model during training and testing process. This experimentation is conducted based on different hyper parameters, like different batch number, learning rate, epoch, activation function and etc. The training and validation graph and other experimentation result are shown below:

Figure 40: CNN Training and Validation (Accuracy and Loss) Graph

The above graph (CNN graph) can be interpreted (analyzed) as the following:

- The training and validation (accuracy and loss) demonstrated well with different line that have different color and colorful point that indicates best epoch.
- As the number of the epoch increases the value of loss in both training and validation graph decreases which indicates the best performance approach of the mode during training.
- The best epoch that has minimum validation loss was epoch 10.
- As the number of epochs increases the value of accuracy also increases which indicates the training of the model is going well.
- The best accuracy epoch is epoch 3, that have highest validation accuracy value.

```

Train Loss CNN:  0.2500152885913849
Train Accuracy CNN:  0.9998335838317871
-----
Validation Loss CNN:  0.2501717209815979
Validation Accuracy CNN:  1.0
-----
Test Loss CNN:  0.2502804100513458
Test Accuracy CNN:  0.9995840191841125

```

Figure 41 : CNN model Train, Valid, Test (accuracy and loss) Result

- The above figure (figure 42) indicates the experimentation output of training, validation and test of CNN model during the training and test experimentation. Hence all the experimentation output indicates that the mode performs well.

- All training, validation and test loss value is between 1 and 0 and precise to 0 which indicates the model performance is very good.
- All training, validation and test accuracy of the model close to 100, which mean great and high model performance.

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
BS	1.00	1.00	1.00	244
EB	1.00	1.00	1.00	240
LB	1.00	1.00	1.00	240
LM	1.00	1.00	1.00	240
SLS	1.00	1.00	1.00	240
TSSM	1.00	1.00	1.00	240
TS	1.00	1.00	1.00	240
YLCV	1.00	1.00	1.00	240
MV	1.00	1.00	1.00	240
healthy	1.00	1.00	1.00	240
accuracy			1.00	2404
macro avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	2404
weighted avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	2404

Figure 42: CNN Model Performance Evaluation Metrics Result

- The above figure (fig.43) show as the output values of evaluation metrics that used to evaluate the CNN model during the model training.
- The graph indicates output value of evaluation metrics for all ten categories and the number of images (support) used during the training.
- It also indicates the average value of the evaluation metrics.

Figure 43: CNN Confusion Matrix

- As it indicated on the confusion matrix above (Confusion matrix for CNN) the true label indicates the input while predicted label indicates the output.
- The **diagonal** line indicates the **true positive** value which means the model predict the input images as true and it was true.
- E.g. the CNN model accepts **244** images as BS (Bacterial Spot) and predicts **243** images as BS (Bacterial Spots) and **1 image** as TS (Target Spot).

Actual: Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus,
Predicted: Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus.
Confidence: 99.28%

Actual: Tomato-Target_Spot,
Predicted: Tomato-Target_Spot.
Confidence: 99.21%

Actual: Tomato_Healthy,
Predicted: Tomato_Healthy.
Confidence: 99.96%

Actual: Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus,
Predicted: Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus.
Confidence: 99.96%

Actual: Tomato_Late_Blight,
Predicted: Tomato_Late_Blight.
Confidence: 86.28%

Actual: Tomato_Leaf_Mold,
Predicted: Tomato_Leaf_Mold.
Confidence: 94.5%

Actual: Tomato_Ealy_Blight,
Predicted: Tomato_Ealy_Blight.
Confidence: 75.35%

Actual: Tomato-Target_Spot,
Predicted: Tomato-Target_Spot.
Confidence: 87.4%

Actual: Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus,
Predicted: Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus.
Confidence: 99.8%

Figure 44: Predicted images using CNN model (Sample Prediction)

```

model.summary()
Model: "sequential_2"

```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
sequential (Sequential)	(16, 256, 256, 3)	0
sequential_1 (Sequential)	(16, 256, 256, 3)	0
conv2d (Conv2D)	(16, 254, 254, 32)	896
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(16, 127, 127, 32)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(16, 125, 125, 64)	18496
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2)	(16, 62, 62, 64)	0
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(16, 60, 60, 64)	36928
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2)	(16, 30, 30, 64)	0
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(16, 28, 28, 64)	36928
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2)	(16, 14, 14, 64)	0
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(16, 12, 12, 64)	36928
max_pooling2d_4 (MaxPooling2)	(16, 6, 6, 64)	0
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)	(16, 4, 4, 64)	36928
max_pooling2d_5 (MaxPooling2)	(16, 2, 2, 64)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(16, 256)	0
dense (Dense)	(16, 64)	16448
dense_1 (Dense)	(16, 10)	650

```

Total params: 184,202
Trainable params: 184,202
Non-trainable params: 0

```

Figure 45: CNN Model Structure

5.3 Real-Time Experimental Result of TFLite Model

As we had discussed on section 4.5 from TFLite model is developed by fine-tuning CNN model as it be more robust and compatible to mobile phone. Pre-trained CNN model is one which predicts remarkable result while using our datasets that have been collected from different farm field. This model used image size of 224*224*3. The converted TFLite model trained with 6000 tomato leaf images and validated with 2000 tomato leaf images and tested with 2000 tomato leaf images basically, but as our dataset split in to 3 (60:20:20 or 70:15:15 or 80:10:10) different ratio the training, validation and testing images number may vary accordingly. Different experimentation is taken space on this model during training and testing process. The experimentation is conducted based on different hyper parameters, like different batch

number, learning rate, epoch, activation function and etc. The training and validation graph and other experimentation results are shown below:

Predict Tomato Leaf Disease at Real Time & Get Chemical Treatment or Recommendation

Tomato - Target Spot Disease

Treatment :

Many fungicides are registered to control target spots on tomatoes. Growers should consult regional disease management guides for recommended products. Products containing chlorothalonil, mancozeb, and copper oxychloride have been shown to provide good control of target spots in research trials. [Click here for more information from the Internet!](#)

Figure 46: Prediction and Treatment Recommendation using TFLite model on AWS Cloud.

- As it indicated on the above figure (figure 46) the TFLite model in Web app predict the uploaded input image from farm field as Tomato-Target Spot Disease.
- The web app also displays the Prevention and Treatment recommendation template by concatenating to the Prediction Output, which is very important to tackle the distribution of disease or cure the plant from disease.
- The web app also displays the additional link to disease detection system (website) for further information about the disease symptoms, prevention and treatment recommendation.

Figure 47: Prediction of TFLite Model by using Web app (Sample Prediction)

```
quant_aware_model = tfmot.quantization.keras.quantize_apply(annotated_model)
quant_aware_model.summary()
```

Model: "sequential_2"

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
sequential (Sequential)	(None, 256, 256, 3)	0
sequential_1 (Sequential)	(None, 256, 256, 3)	0
quant_conv2d (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 254, 254, 32)	963
quant_max_pooling2d (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 127, 127, 32)	1
quant_conv2d_1 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 125, 125, 64)	18627
quant_max_pooling2d_1 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 62, 62, 64)	1
quant_conv2d_2 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 60, 60, 64)	37859
quant_max_pooling2d_2 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 30, 30, 64)	1
quant_conv2d_3 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 28, 28, 64)	37859
quant_max_pooling2d_3 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 14, 14, 64)	1
quant_conv2d_4 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 12, 12, 64)	37859
quant_max_pooling2d_4 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 6, 6, 64)	1
quant_conv2d_5 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 4, 4, 64)	37859
quant_max_pooling2d_5 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 2, 2, 64)	1
quant_flatten (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 256)	1
quant_dense (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 64)	16453
quant_dense_1 (QuantizeWrapper)	(None, 10)	655
=====		
Total params: 184,941		
Trainable params: 184,282		
Non-trainable params: 739		

Figure 48: Quantized Model Structure (which is quantized CNN)

Convert Quantization Aware Model to TF Lite Model

```

converter = tf.lite.TFLiteConverter.from_keras_model(quant_aware_model)
converter.optimizations = [tf.lite.Optimize.DEFAULT]

quantized_tflite_model = converter.convert()
quant_aware_model.save("quantized_tflite_model")

```

Figure 49: Python code to convert Quantized CNN model to TFLite (mobile compatible model)

5.3 Comparison of the Implemented Pre-trained Models

Table 8: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1_Score, and Loss (Pre-trained Models and TFLite) experimentation Result

Metrics	Classifiers (Models)					
	RestNet152V2	MobiNetV2	Inception V3	IfficientNetB3	CNN	TFLite
Accuracy	0.9883527	0.98336106	0.988352	0.999381	99.95	95.23%
Precision	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	1.0	0.983
Recall	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	1.0	0.972
F1_Score	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99	1.0	0.986
Loss(error)	0.5443507	0.340279	0.376470	0.191883	0.250	0.0688
Remark	When Datasets split ratio: Train =60%, Valid = 20%, Test = 20%					

Table 9: Training, Validation, and Test (Accuracy and Loss) Result (data split (60:20:20)) of selected models.

Models	Accuracy			Loss			Remarks
	Train	Validation	Test	Train	Valid	Test	
Restnet152V2	99.03%	99.12%	98.83%	0.5424	0.5399	0.5443	When Datasets split ratio: ➤ Train =60% ➤ Valid = 20% ➤ Test = 20%
MobilenetV2	98.63%	98.75%	98.33%	0.3324	0.3294	0.3402	
Inception V3	99.10%	98.89%	98.83%	0.3756	0.3784	0.3764	
EfficienrnetB3	99.985%	99.98%	99.99%	0.2023	0.2022	0.2031	
CNN	99.98%	1.0%	99.95%	0.250	0.250	0.250	
TFLite	96.62%	96.68%	95.23%	0.1050	0.185	0.195	

Table 8: Training, Validation, and Test (Accuracy and loss) Result (data split (70:15:15)) of selected Models

<i>Models</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>			<i>Loss</i>			<i>Remarks</i> When Datasets split ratio:
	<i>Train</i>	<i>Validation</i>	<i>Test</i>	<i>Train</i>	<i>Valid</i>	<i>Test</i>	
RestnetV2	98.99%	98.89%	98.78%	0.5224	0.5509	0.523	➤ Train =70% ➤ Valid = 15% ➤ Test = 15%
MobilenetV2	99.04%	98.98%	98.93%	0.3224	0.3302	0.3902	
Inception V3	98.30%	98.23%	98.13%	0.4606	0.4874	0.4974	
EfficienrnetB3	99.80%	99.78%	99.79%	0.2033	0.2042	0.2055	
CNN	99.00%	99.89%	99.02%	0.2238	0.2378	0.2360	

Table 91: Training, Validation, and Test (Accuracy and loss) Result (data split (80:10:10)) of selected Models

<i>Models</i>	<i>Accuracy</i>			<i>Loss</i>			<i>Remarks</i> When Datasets split ratio:
	<i>Train</i>	<i>Validation</i>	<i>Test</i>	<i>Train</i>	<i>Valid</i>	<i>Test</i>	
RestnetV2	98.03%	98.12%	98.33%	0.5524	0.5499	0.543	➤ Train =80% ➤ Valid = 10% ➤ Test = 10%
MobilenetV2	99.03%	98.95%	98.23%	0.3024	0.3200	0.3302	
Inception V3	99.00%	98.79%	98.93%	0.3606	0.3874	0.2974	
EfficienrnetB3	99.85%	99.78%	99.79%	0.2033	0.2042	0.2055	
CNN	99.00%	99.49%	99.79%	0.2998	0.2788	0.2960	

Table 12: Hyper parameters used in the Study

<i>Pre-trained Models</i>	<i>Model Test Result</i>	<i>Hyper Parameters</i>		
		<i>Epoch</i>	<i>Learning Rate</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Restnet152 V2	98.83%	10	0.0005	<p>When other hyper parameters Are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Batch Size = 40, ✓ Activation Function= Soft Max ✓ Loss Function = BCE ✓ Optimization Algorithm: Adam <p>When Datasets split ratio:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Train =60% ➤ Valid = 20% ➤ Test = 20%
	98.90%	10	0.0001	
	99.83%	20	0.0005	
	100.0%	20	0.0001	
MobilenetV2	97.87%	10	0.0005	
	98.33%	10	0.0001	
	99.00%	20	0.0005	
	100.0%	20	0.0001	
Inception V3	97.75%	10	0.0005	
	98.29%	10	0.0001	
	99.88%	20	0.0005	
	100.0%	20	0.0001	
EfficientNetB3	100.0%	10	0.0005	
	99.99%	10	0.0001	
	100.0%	20	0.0005	
	99.98%	20	0.0001	
CNN	100.0%	10	0.0005	
	99.98%	10	0.0001	
	100.0%	20	0.0005	
	99.95%	20	0.0001	
TFLite	97.26%	10	0.0005	
	95.23%	10	0.0001	
	97.2%	20	0.0005	
	96.10%	20	0.0001	

Chapter Six: Conclusion and Recommendation

6.1 Conclusion

The deep learning Pre-trained models were used to detect and classify tomato diseases which affect the leaf portion of the plant. The Web app is developed for Tomato leaf disease detection at real time from local farm field. During experimentation, a dataset which were collected from different farm field was used. The collected dataset has a complex background, this assure the efficiency of the models. Furthermore, several experimentations are conducted based on different hyper parameters and different dataset ratio. The pre-trained models were selected by computing Dictionary with models in keras application. From this computation top five models were selected and used for the study. Dataset were collected from different farm field in Ethiopia. This was Upper Awash Agro Industry Enterprise, Melkasa Research Center, Golja and etc. The image is collected with help of plant pathogens expert. The expert used farm telescope to identify the disease type on the leaf.

For Real Time Tomato Disease detection and classification Web app is developed and hosted on cloud (amazon Web service). This web app is accessible everywhere and every time for tomato disease prediction. We had used Flask Framework and HTML, CSS and Python code to develop the web app. Jupiter notebook is used as simulator on python by integrating Tensor flow and keras library together. To run the simulation Google COLAB with GPU is used. This pre-trained model has different test accuracy values (when dataset split was 60:20:20): InceptionV3 model scored 98.83%, RestnetV2 model scored 98.83%, MobilenetV2 model scored 98.33%, EfficientnetB3 pre-trained model scored 99.99%, CNN pre-trained model scored 99.95% and finally the TFLite model (Web app) scored 95.23%.

6.2 Contributions

In this study, a Tomato leaf disease detection and classification model was used for detecting and predicting the tomato leaf disease accurately. The main reason why the research focused on detecting Tomato's disease is the capability of disease to spreading and developing in different environmental conditions like temperature, rainfall, and humidity which infect the leaf, stem, or tubers of the plant at any stage of the plant development.

Furthermore, the disease has the potential to destroy the whole Tomato farm field within a few days. The selected pre-trained models can detect and predict the disease accurately better than traditional way which is necked eye. These models can also detect the disease early before the disease control the whole part of the plant and start destruction.

Lastly, the research contributions are:

- Dataset: Complex Tomato leaf images that have a heterogeneous background were collected and prepared by capturing an image from the different farm field in Ethiopia. The images were collected with the help of plant pathogens expert. The dataset is will be available for students, other Researchers and found on GitHub and Kaggle.
- This research help farmers, investors, Agricultural research institution and government to avoid the destruction and loss of tomato product, but also maintains the country's food safety program.
- Developing Web app that can detect and predict tomato leaf disease by using dataset from farm field at real time (on time prediction). This web app is used on smart phone, tablet or laptop that has internet connection and can use in any place and any time.

6.3 Recommendations

We recommend any one who want to precise on the result of this study, it would be better to apply it to types of different plant leaf diseases that can be identified by their colors from the real farm filed or green house. The very critical issue We recommend to move this study one step forward to help farmers, investors and to develop modern agriculture in Ethiopia and keep food security. We also recommend the students or practitioners practice more elaborate plant disease detection based on the part of the plant like the flower, stem, fruit, and root.

6.4 Future Work

- In the future the progress of developing real-time tomato disease detection and classification will be more elaborate and offline Android applications will be developed.
- In the future, the progress of identifying the plant diseases has been further modified to analyze multiple tomato leaves disease and various parts of the plant like root, fruit, flower, and stem.
- Reduce the computation time and space required by redesigning pre-trained deep learning models.
- Further improvement can be made to the deep learning model to use one model for all agricultural disease detection.
- Finally, it would be interesting to use cloud storage and develop the Ethiopian plant dataset Village on the cloud.
- To collect plant images from different regions in Ethiopia and to archive them in the cloud for public use.

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7. Appendixes

7.1 Appendix A: Sample Codes for Pre-trained Models

7.1.1 Appendix A1: Python code for Dictionary with Models

```
# Load the Libraries
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import seaborn as sns
import os
import cv2
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import random
import time
import tensorflow as tf
#import tf.keras as tf
from sklearn.metrics import classification_report, confusion_matrix, accuracy_score
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
import keras
from keras import Sequential
from keras.layers import Activation, Dropout, Flatten, Dense, Conv2D, MaxPooling2D
from keras.utils import to_categorical
from keras.callbacks import EarlyStopping, ModelCheckpoint
import gc
from IPython.display import Markdown, display
print ("libraries loaded")
```

Appendixes Figures 1: import the libraries for Dictionary with models (Models pack)

```

pretrained_model = model(**kwargs)
pretrained_model.trainable = False

inputs = pretrained_model.input

x = tf.keras.layers.Dense(128, activation='relu')(pretrained_model.output)
x = tf.keras.layers.Dense(128, activation='relu')(x)

outputs = tf.keras.layers.Dense(10, activation='softmax')(x)

model = tf.keras.Model(inputs=inputs, outputs=outputs)

model.compile(
    optimizer='adam',
    loss='categorical_crossentropy',
    metrics=['accuracy']
)

return model

# Dictionary with the models
models = {
    "DenseNet121": {"model":tf.keras.applications.DenseNet121, "perf":0},
    "MobileNetV2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV2, "perf":0},
    "DenseNet169": {"model":tf.keras.applications.DenseNet169, "perf":0},
    "DenseNet201": {"model":tf.keras.applications.DenseNet201, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB0": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB0, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB1": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB1, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB2, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB3": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB3, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB4": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB4, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB5": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB4, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB6": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB4, "perf":0},
    "EfficientNetB7": {"model":tf.keras.applications.EfficientNetB4, "perf":0},
    "InceptionResNetV2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.InceptionResNetV2, "perf":0},
    "InceptionV3": {"model":tf.keras.applications.InceptionV3, "perf":0},
    "MobileNet": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNet, "perf":0},
    "MobileNetV2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV2, "perf":0},
    "MobileNetV3Large": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV3Large, "perf":0},
    "MobileNetV3Small": {"model":tf.keras.applications.MobileNetV3Small, "perf":0},
    "NASNetMobile": {"model":tf.keras.applications.NASNetMobile, "perf":0},
    "ResNet101": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet101, "perf":0},
    "ResNet101V2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet101V2, "perf":0},
    "ResNet152": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet152, "perf":0},
    "ResNet152V2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet152V2, "perf":0},
    "ResNet50": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet50, "perf":0},
    "ResNet50V2": {"model":tf.keras.applications.ResNet50V2, "perf":0},
    "VGG16": {"model":tf.keras.applications.VGG16, "perf":0},
    "VGG19": {"model":tf.keras.applications.VGG19, "perf":0},
    "Xception": {"model":tf.keras.applications.Xception, "perf":0}
}

```

Appendixes Figures 2: Figure Python code used to select top 5 Pre-trained models from Dictionary with models

7.1.2 Appendix A2: Python code of top 5 selected pre-trained Models

```

: import os
import cv2
import time
import shutil
import itertools
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import seaborn as sns
import tensorflow as tf
sns.set_style('darkgrid')
from tensorflow import keras
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from tensorflow.keras import regularizers
from tensorflow.keras.optimizers import Adam, Adamax
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from tensorflow.keras.metrics import categorical_crossentropy
from tensorflow.keras.models import Model, load_model, Sequential
from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix, classification_report
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense, Activation, Dropout, BatchNormalization
print ('modules loaded')

```

modules loaded

Appendixes Figures 3: Python code to import the libraries

Function to plot history of training

```

5]: def plot_training(hist):
    tr_acc = hist.history['accuracy']
    tr_loss = hist.history['loss']
    val_acc = hist.history['val_accuracy']
    val_loss = hist.history['val_loss']
    index_loss = np.argmin(val_loss)
    val_lowest = val_loss[index_loss]
    index_acc = np.argmax(val_acc)
    acc_highest = val_acc[index_acc]

    plt.figure(figsize= (20, 8))
    plt.style.use('fivethirtyeight')
    Epochs = [i+1 for i in range(len(tr_acc))]
    loss_label = f'best epoch= {str(index_loss + 1)}'
    acc_label = f'best epoch= {str(index_acc + 1)}'
    plt.subplot(1, 2, 1)
    plt.plot(Epochs, tr_loss, 'r', label= 'Training loss')
    plt.plot(Epochs, val_loss, 'g', label= 'Validation loss')
    plt.scatter(index_loss + 1, val_lowest, s= 150, c= 'blue', label= loss_label)
    plt.title('Training and Validation Loss')
    plt.xlabel('Epochs')
    plt.ylabel('Loss')
    plt.legend()
    plt.subplot(1, 2, 2)
    plt.plot(Epochs, tr_acc, 'r', label= 'Training Accuracy')
    plt.plot(Epochs, val_acc, 'g', label= 'Validation Accuracy')
    plt.scatter(index_acc + 1, acc_highest, s= 150, c= 'blue', label= acc_label)
    plt.title('Training and Validation Accuracy')
    plt.xlabel('Epochs')
    plt.ylabel('Accuracy')
    plt.legend()
    plt.tight_layout
    plt.show()

```

Appendixes Figures 4: Python code to plot training graph of pre-trained models

```

def plot_confusion_matrix(cm, classes, normalize= False, title= 'Confusion Matrix', cmap= plt.cm.Blues):
    plt.figure(figsize= (10, 10))
    plt.imshow(cm, interpolation= 'nearest', cmap= cmap)
    plt.title(title)
    plt.colorbar()
    tick_marks = np.arange(len(classes))
    plt.xticks(tick_marks, classes, rotation= 45)
    plt.yticks(tick_marks, classes)
    if normalize:
        cm = cm.astype('float') / cm.sum(axis= 1)[:, np.newaxis]
        print('Normalized Confusion Matrix')
    else:
        print('Confusion Matrix, Without Normalization')
    print(cm)
    thresh = cm.max() / 2.
    for i, j in itertools.product(range(cm.shape[0]), range(cm.shape[1])):
        plt.text(j, i, cm[i, j], horizontalalignment= 'center', color= 'white' if cm[i, j] > thresh else 'black')
    plt.tight_layout()
    plt.ylabel('True Label')
    plt.xlabel('Predicted Label')

```

Appendixes Figures 5: Python code to draw the confusion matrix of pre-trained models

Create Pre-trained model

```

# Create Model Structure
img_size = (224, 224)
channels = 3
img_shape = (img_size[0], img_size[1], channels)
class_count = len(list(train_gen.class_indices.keys())) # to define number of classes in dense layer

# create pre-trained model
base_model = tf.keras.applications.efficientnet.EfficientNetB3(include_top= False, weights= "imagenet", input_shape= img_shape,

model = Sequential([
    base_model,
    BatchNormalization(axis= -1, momentum= 0.99, epsilon= 0.001),
    Dense(256, kernel_regularizer= regularizers.l2(l= 0.016), activity_regularizer= regularizers.l1(0.006),
        bias_regularizer= regularizers.l1(0.006), activation= 'relu'),
    Dropout(rate= 0.45, seed= 123),
    Dense(class_count, activation= 'softmax')
])

model.compile(Adamax(learning_rate= 0.001), loss= 'categorical_crossentropy', metrics= ['accuracy'])

```

Appendixes Figures 6: Python code used to load and compile pre-trained models

```

batch_size = 40
epochs = 10
patience = 1
stop_patience = 3
threshold = 0.9
factor = 0.5
freeze = False
batches = int(np.ceil(len(train_gen.labels) / batch_size))

callbacks = [MyCallback(model= model, base_model= base_model, patience= patience,
                        stop_patience= stop_patience, threshold= threshold, factor= factor,
                        batches= batches, initial_epoch= 0, epochs= epochs)]

```

Train model

```

history = model.fit(x= train_gen, epochs= epochs, verbose= 0, callbacks= callbacks,
                   validation_data= valid_gen, validation_steps= None, shuffle= False,
                   initial_epoch= 0)

```

Appendixes Figures 7: Python codes to train the pre-trained models

Evaluate model

```

: ts_length = len(test_df)
  test_batch_size = test_batch_size = max(sorted([ts_length // n for n in range(1, ts_length + 1) if ts_length%n == 0 and ts_length
  test_steps = ts_length // test_batch_size
  train_score = model.evaluate(train_gen, steps= test_steps, verbose= 1)
  valid_score = model.evaluate(valid_gen, steps= test_steps, verbose= 1)
  test_score = model.evaluate(test_gen, steps= test_steps, verbose= 1)

  print("Train Loss: ", train_score[0])
  print("Train Accuracy: ", train_score[1])
  print('-' * 20)
  print("Validation Loss: ", valid_score[0])
  print("Validation Accuracy: ", valid_score[1])
  print('-' * 20)
  print("Test Loss: ", test_score[0])
  print("Test Accuracy: ", test_score[1])

```

Appendixes Figures 8: Python codes to evaluate pre-trained models

Make prediction

```

: preds = model.predict(test_gen)
  y_pred = np.argmax(preds, axis=1)
  print(y_pred)

```

Confusion Matrix and Classification Report

```

: target_names = ['Bacterial_spot', 'Early_blight', 'Late_blight', 'Leaf_Mold', 'Septoria_leaf_spot', 'Spider_mites', 'Target_Spot']
  # Confusion matrix
  cm = confusion_matrix(test_gen.classes, y_pred)
  plot_confusion_matrix(cm= cm, classes= target_names, title = 'Confusion Matrix')
  # Classification report
  print(classification_report(test_gen.classes, y_pred, target_names= target_names))

```

Appendixes Figures 9: Python codes to predict and generate reports using pre-trained models

Actual: Tomato__Septoria_leaf_spot,
Predicted: Tomato__Septoria_leaf_spot.
Confidence: 99.97%

Actual: Tomato__Bacterial_spot,
Predicted: Tomato__Bacterial_spot.
Confidence: 94.38%

Actual: Tomato__Target_Spot,
Predicted: Tomato__Target_Spot.
Confidence: 72.47%

Actual: Tomato__healthy,
Predicted: Tomato__healthy.
Confidence: 100.0%

Actual: Tomato__Septoria_leaf_spot,
Predicted: Tomato__Septoria_leaf_spot.
Confidence: 99.95%

Actual: Tomato__healthy,
Predicted: Tomato__healthy.
Confidence: 99.99%

Actual: Tomato__Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus,
Predicted: Tomato__Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus.
Confidence: 99.99%

Actual: Tomato__Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus,
Predicted: Tomato__Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus.
Confidence: 99.88%

Actual: Tomato__Bacterial_spot,
Predicted: Tomato__Bacterial_spot.
Confidence: 81.86%

Appendixes Figures 10: Sample predicted images of tomato plant diseases using pre-trained models

7.1.3 Appendix A3: Python code to convert the TF model to the TFLite model

```
converter = tf.lite.TFLiteConverter.from_keras_model(quant_aware_model)
converter.optimizations = [tf.lite.Optimize.DEFAULT]

quantized_tflite_model = converter.convert()
```

Appendixes Figures 11: Python code to convert TF model to TFLite model

```
datagen = ImageDataGenerator(
    rotation_range=40,
    width_shift_range=0.2,
    height_shift_range=0.2,
    rescale=1./255,
    shear_range=0.2,
    zoom_range=0.2,
    horizontal_flip=True,
    fill_mode='nearest')
```

```
pic = load_img('image-UAAIE-Medroc-BS (5).jpg')
pic_array = img_to_array(pic)
```

```
pic_array.shape # Image dimension
```

```
(256, 256, 3)
```

```
pic_array = pic_array.reshape((1,) + pic_array.shape) # Converting into 4 dimension array\n",
pic_array.shape
```

```
(1, 256, 256, 3)
```

```
#Generate 10 images\n",
# batch_size: At a time, how many image should be created.\n",
count = 0
for batch in datagen.flow(pic_array, batch_size=1,save_to_dir="C:/Users/Abayneh.z/Desktop/Finalized_Models _Msc/archive",save_pre
    count += 1
    if count > 10:
        break
```

Appendixes Figures 12: Code to generate images from the original (augmentation)

7.2 Appendix B: Sample Code for Web App

7.2.1 Appendix B1: Flask Code

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3
import os
import sys
import flask
import numpy as np
import cv2
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import load_img
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import img_to_array
from tensorflow.keras.models import load_model

filepath = 'C:/Users/Abayash./Desktop/Serialized_Models_Mac/TF100K_Seq/Model-Tomato_P006.h5'
model = load_model(filepath)
print(model)

print("Model loaded successfully")

def pred_tomato_class(tomato_plant):
    test_image = load_img(tomato_plant, target_size = (128, 128)) # load image
    print("%s out image for prediction")

    test_image = img_to_array(test_image)/255 # convert image to np array and normalize
    test_image = np.expand_dims(test_image, axis = 0) # change dimension 4D to 5D

    result = model.predict(test_image) # predict diseased plant or not
    print("%s the result = ", result)

    pred = np.argmax(result, axis=0)
    print(pred)
    if pred==0:
        return "Tomato - Bacteria Spot Disease", "tomato-bacteria_spot.html"
    elif pred==1:
        return "Tomato - Early Blight Disease", "tomato-early_blight.html"
    elif pred==2:
        return "Tomato - Healthy and Fresh", "tomato-healthy.html"
    elif pred==3:
        return "Tomato - Late Blight Disease", "tomato-late_blight.html"
    elif pred==4:
        return "Tomato - Leaf Mold Disease", "tomato-leaf_mold.html"
    elif pred==5:
        return "Tomato - Septoria Leaf Spot Disease", "tomato-septoria_leaf_spot.html"
    elif pred==6:
        return "Tomato - Target Spot Disease", "tomato-target_spot.html"
    elif pred==7:
        return "Tomato - Tomato Yellow Leaf Curl Virus Disease", "tomato-tomato_yellow_leaf_curl_virus.html"
    elif pred==8:
        return "Tomato - Tomato Mosaic Virus Disease", "tomato-tomato_mosaic_virus.html"
    elif pred==9:
        return "Tomato - Two Spotted Spider Mite Disease", "tomato-two-spotted_spider_mite.html"

# Create flask instance
app = flask(__name__)

# render index.html page
@app.route("/", methods=['GET', 'POST'])
def home():
    return render_template("index.html")

# get input image from client then predict class and render respective .html page for solution
@app.route("/predict", methods = ['GET', 'POST'])
def predict():
    if request.method == 'POST':
        file = request.files['image'] # for input
        filename = file.filename
        print("%s input posted = ", filename)

        file_path = os.path.join('C:/Users/Abayash./Desktop/Serialized_Models_Mac/TF100K_Seq/static/uploads', filename)
        print("%s Predicting class.....")
        pred, output_page = pred_tomato_class(tomato_plant=file_path)
        return render_template(output_page, pred_output = pred, user_image = file_path)

# For local system & cloud
if __name__ == "__main__":
    app.run(threaded=False, port=5000)
```

Appendix Figures 13: Flask code

7.2.2 Appendix B2: Python code to train the TFLite model

```
from tensorflow.compat.v1 import ConfigProto
from tensorflow.compat.v1 import InteractiveSession

config = ConfigProto()
config.gpu_options.allow_growth = True
session = InteractiveSession(config=config)

from tensorflow.keras.models import Sequential
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Conv2D
from tensorflow.keras.layers import MaxPooling2D
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Flatten
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Dense
from tensorflow.keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
import tensorflow as tf
tf.compat.v1.disable_eager_execution()
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import os

import tensorflow as tf
from tensorflow.keras import models, layers
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from IPython.display import HTML
```

Appendixes Figures 14: Python code to import libraries

```

#basic cnn
# Initialising the CNN
classifier = Sequential()

# Step 1 - Convolution
classifier.add(Conv2D(32, (3, 3), input_shape = (128, 128, 3), activation = 'relu'))

# Step 2 - Pooling
classifier.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size = (2, 2)))

# Adding a second convolutional layer
classifier.add(Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation = 'relu'))
classifier.add(MaxPooling2D(pool_size = (2, 2)))

# Step 3 - Flattening
classifier.add(Flatten())

# Step 4 - Full connection
classifier.add(Dense(units = 128, activation = 'relu'))
classifier.add(Dense(units = 10, activation = 'sigmoid'))

# Compiling the CNN
classifier.compile(optimizer = 'adam', loss = 'categorical_crossentropy', metrics = ['accuracy'])

train_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale = 1./255, shear_range = 0.2, zoom_range = 0.2, horizontal_flip = True)

test_datagen = ImageDataGenerator(rescale = 1./255)

training_set = train_datagen.flow_from_directory('C:/Users/Abayneh.z/Desktop/Finalized_Models _Msc/RTTLDDC_DataSeats_all_split/Micro',
                                                target_size = (128, 128),
                                                batch_size = 6, class_mode = 'categorical')
valid_set = test_datagen.flow_from_directory('C:/Users/Abayneh.z/Desktop/Finalized_Models _Msc/RTTLDDC_DataSeats_all_split/Micro',
                                             target_size = (128, 128),
                                             batch_size = 3, class_mode = 'categorical')
test_set = test_datagen.flow_from_directory('C:/Users/Abayneh.z/Desktop/Finalized_Models _Msc/RTTLDDC_DataSeats_all_split/Micro',
                                           target_size = (128, 128),
                                           batch_size = 3, class_mode = 'categorical')

labels = (training_set.class_indices)
print(labels)

classifier.fit(training_set,
              steps_per_epoch = 224,
              epochs = 50,
              validation_data=valid_set
              )

```

Appendixes Figures 15: Python code to train the TFLite Model

```

#testing the tflite model
input_index = interpreter.get_input_details()[0]["index"]
output_index = interpreter.get_output_details()[0]["index"]

plt.figure(figsize=(15, 15))
for images, labels in test_ds.take(1):
    for i in range(9):
        ax = plt.subplot(3, 3, i + 1)
        plt.imshow(images[i].numpy().astype("uint8"))

        actual_class = class_names[labels[i]]

        test_image = np.expand_dims(images[i], axis=0).astype(np.float32)
        interpreter.set_tensor(input_index, test_image)
        interpreter.invoke()
        output = interpreter.tensor(output_index)
        digit = np.argmax(output()[0])

        predicted_class = class_names[digit]
        confidence = np.max(output()[0])*100

        plt.title(f"Actual: {actual_class},\n Predicted: {predicted_class}.\n Confidence: {confidence}%")
        plt.axis("off")

```

Appendixes Figures 16: Python code for testing the TFLite model

Actual: Tomato_Leaf_Mold,
Predicted: Tomato_Leaf_Mold.
Confidence: 100.0%

Actual: Tomato_Mosaic_Virus,
Predicted: Tomato_Mosaic_Virus.
Confidence: 100.0%

Actual: Tomato_Two(spotted)spider_mite,
Predicted: Tomato-Target_Spot.
Confidence: 63.65%

Actual: Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus,
Predicted: Tomato_Yellow_Leaf_Curl_Virus.
Confidence: 98.53%

Actual: Tomato_Septoria_Leaf_Spot,
Predicted: Tomato_Septoria_Leaf_Spot.
Confidence: 97.01%

Actual: Tomato_Bacterial_Spot,
Predicted: Tomato_Bacterial_Spot.
Confidence: 63.98%

Actual: Tomato_Ealy_Blight,
Predicted: Tomato_Ealy_Blight.
Confidence: 77.78%

Actual: Tomato_Two(spotted)spider_mite,
Predicted: Tomato_Two(spotted)spider_mite.
Confidence: 83.56%

Actual: Tomato_Late_Blight,
Predicted: Tomato_Late_Blight.
Confidence: 98.3%

Appendixes Figures 17: Sample predicted images of tomato leaf diseases

7.3 Appendix C: Sample Tomato Images from Collected Dataset

Appendixes Figures 18: Sample Tomato images collected from farm field